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**ENRICHING CULTURAL HERITAGE
THROUGH SEMANTIC ANNOTATIONS:
PROTOTYPING AND VISUALIZING
COMPLEX INFORMATION IN THE
DIGITAL HUMANITIES**

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Introduction

Cultural heritage institutions—Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums (GLAMs)—play a crucial role in preserving and disseminating knowledge. These institutions have long been at the forefront of developing standards for interoperability and accessibility, ensuring that cultural artifacts remain available for research, education, and public engagement. However, the rapid advancement of digital technologies presents both new opportunities and challenges in the representation, structuring, and dissemination of cultural heritage data. One of the most persistent challenges has been the siloed nature of institutional databases, which often results in fragmented and non-interoperable knowledge systems.

Historically, Digital Humanities (DH) research has primarily focused on text analysis, developing tools and methodologies for structuring and exploring textual corpora. In contrast, images—despite their centrality to cultural heritage—have often been treated as supplementary elements in cataloging records rather than as complex, knowledge-rich objects in their own right. This thesis investigates how knowledge representation techniques can enhance the semantic depth and interpretative potential of digital images, acknowledging the multi-layered nature of visual content.

A central focus of this research is IIF (International Image Interoperability Framework)—a framework that has transformed the delivery, annotation, and curation of digital images. Often referred to as IIF (generally pronounced “triple-eye-eff”), this framework promotes open, shared, and scalable image delivery solutions, fostering interoperability among institutions and creating new avenues for scholarly engagement. The underlying philosophy of IIF aligns with the broader shift toward developer-centered usability, a principle exemplified by projects like Linked Art, which prioritize the role of developers as key intermediaries between knowledge producers (institutions) and knowledge consumers (scholars). In many DH discussions, developers are often overlooked, despite their crucial role in transforming raw institutional data into usable, structured formats. By emphasizing usability and adopting web-native formats such as JSON-LD, Linked Art and similar initiatives make structured cultural heritage data more accessible to broader audiences, including those outside domain expertise.

Beyond the question of data usability, this thesis also explores how annotations—widely used by scholars across disciplines—can serve as tools for creating and structuring new knowledge. Annotations, particularly those applied to images, enable interpretative engagement, transforming visual data into semantically enriched, machine-readable information. However, annotation in cultural heritage and art history is inherently subjective and interpretative, differing from the deterministic data structures commonly found in empirical sciences. While scientific methodologies

remain foundational across disciplines, the uncertainty, provenance, and interpretative nature of humanities data introduce a distinct epistemological challenge. Rather than treating these aspects as limitations, this thesis argues that uncertainty and interpretative plurality can be modeled and visualized explicitly, offering a richer and more transparent representation of cultural knowledge.

To integrate these insights into a practical framework, this thesis proposes LISA (Linked Interpretative Semantic Annotation Model)—a new model for representing and structuring iconographical annotations of artworks. LISA builds on existing ontological patterns while incorporating new experimental approaches in image interpretation, providing scholars with a flexible and semantically expressive tool to enrich IIF images with interpretative data.

The conceptual foundation of LISA is further explored through semiotics and hermeneutics, demonstrating how visual interpretation principles can inform user experience (UX) design in annotation interfaces. As a final step in this research, a prototype for a collaborative annotation tool, VISTA (Visual Interpretative Semantic Tagging Application), is designed. VISTA implements Panofsky's three-level iconographical framework within an interactive and semantically enriched IIF-based annotation environment. By incorporating semantic annotation, structured data usability, and visualization techniques, this prototype aims to redefine how digital humanities platforms approach image-based interpretation.

The goal of this research is to contribute to an ongoing discussion on the potential of semantic annotation in the digital humanities, specifically regarding how structured, interoperable data formats like JSON-LD can enhance scholarly engagement with images. Furthermore, it examines how data visualization can move beyond static representation, becoming an active part of the interpretative process itself. By bridging knowledge representation, UX design, and cultural heritage annotation, this thesis seeks to advance both technical and conceptual frameworks for image-based scholarship in the digital age.

1. Images in GLAM: Models and Visualization

1.1 The role of GLAMs institutions

When discussing cultural heritage and the role of Digital Humanities (DH), it is essential to understand the meaning and role of institutions. It is now widely accepted to refer, using the acronym GLAM, to institutions such as Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums. We need to ask ourselves what those entities have in common, so much so that they have been grouped. GLAM institutions share a common mission: to preserve and provide access to knowledge and cultural heritage. The term “GLAM” represents an evolution from the earlier “LAM”, or occasionally “E-LAM”, which was introduced in the 1990s to represent Libraries, Archives, and Museums. These institutions recognized their overlapping roles, particularly in terms of the preservation and accessibility of information and cultural heritage objects.

With the advent of the *World-Wide Web* (Berners-Lee et al. 1992), institutions increasingly began digitizing their collections, gradually recognizing their interconnected roles around digital preservation, information retrieval, and public access. By the 2000s, as digital and online initiatives grew to incorporate art galleries and exhibition spaces, the “G” for Galleries was added to acknowledge the presence of visual arts within these domains.

Two essential aspects connect these cultural heritage institutions under the common GLAM framework: **information science** and **collaboration**. While information science has always been a focal point of these institutions, with the advent of the Semantic Web (Shadbolt, Berners-Lee, and Hall 2003), the collaborative aspect has also become a priority among these institutions. The importance of collaboration and knowledge sharing across GLAM institutions was extensively analyzed in the 2008 report *“Beyond the Silos of the LAMs: Collaboration Among Libraries, Archives, and Museums”* (Zorich, Waibel, and Erway 2008). The report underscores how cross-institutional partnerships can significantly enhance the management, accessibility, and dissemination of cultural heritage. It highlights that museums, libraries, and archives can each leverage their respective methodologies to strengthen their institutional roles. For instance, museums could adopt library methodologies to enhance collection accessibility, while libraries and archives could incorporate museums’ strategies for education and community engagement, fostering a more collaborative and integrated approach.

This collaborative ethos is further reinforced by the **International Council of Museums (ICOM)**¹, whose 2022 definition of “museum” explicitly acknowledges its educational, ethical, and social role:

“A museum is a not-for-profit, permanent institution in the service of society that researches, collects, conserves, interprets, and exhibits tangible and intangible heritage. Open to the public, accessible, and inclusive, museums foster diversity and sustainability. They operate and communicate ethically, professionally and with the participation of communities, offering varied experiences for education, enjoyment, reflection and knowledge sharing.” (Extraordinary General Assembly 2022)

Within this context, information management—spanning the collection, conservation, and exhibition of both tangible and intangible heritage—has long been a cornerstone of GLAM institutions. Information science, as Harold Borko defines it, is a discipline concerned with *“the properties and behavior of information, the forces governing the flow of information, and the means of processing information for optimum accessibility and usability.”* (Borko 1968, 3). It encompasses all stages of the information life cycle—from collection and organization to retrieval, transformation, and utilization.

In GLAMs, therefore, it is essential to address the entire life cycle of information, particularly as it applies to visual objects and their representation. As Arlene G. Taylor emphasizes in *“The Organization of Information”* (Taylor 2004), understanding the structure and management of information is central to the functioning of libraries, archives, and museums, where specialized practices for visual items and metadata continue to evolve in response to digital and semantic web technologies.

From a historical point of view, even before the widespread adoption of computational techniques, archives and libraries were the first to experiment with early models of online public access catalog (OPAC) models in the ‘60s. In the same years, the *Library of Congress* created the **MARC**² format for representing bibliographic information. These electronic implementations were the evolution of what already began at the end of the 19th century, demonstrating the deep connection between information science and documentation science, since classification systems like the **Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC)** (Dewey 1876) were starting to be approached in libraries. From that early experiment in the formalized sharing of information, the DH sector has always been prone to

¹ <https://icom.museum/>

² <https://www.loc.gov/marc>

investigate a way of managing and sharing information, and with the evolution of electronic methods, new possibilities, and challenges arise. In the '80s markup languages such as **SGML**³ (1986) and the first **TEI**⁴ initiatives (1987) had the purpose to enhance interoperability and to release the data from the software capable of reading it, creating a vocabulary for interchange. It is with the **Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records**, be **FRBR** (IFLA Study Group on the Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records 1998), that GLAM institutions address the need to develop formal models for describing not only bibliographic content but also the information conveyed through material sources.

The real collaboration possibilities and connections began to emerge with the application of the **Semantic Web Stack**⁵ to DH projects. This stack is grounded in the principles of **conceptualization** and **abstraction**, transforming theoretical considerations on knowledge representation and semantic rules into technical specifications and practical solutions. These principles found their actualization in technological tools and standards, such as **URIs (Uniform Resource Identifiers)** and **IRIs (Internationalized Resource Identifiers)** for unique identification of resources, **HTTP (Hypertext Transfer Protocol)** as the protocol of data transmission, **Unicode** for character encoding, **XML (Extensible Markup Language)** as a markup language for data exchange, and **RDF (Resource Description Framework)** for knowledge representation based on triples. RDF serializations and higher-level constructs, such as **OWL (Web Ontology Language)**, **RDFS (RDF Schema)**, and **SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System)**, enable the creation of ontologies and schemas, serving as the foundation of the Semantic Web's approach to data representation and interlinking.

The emphasis on collaboration is particularly significant in the context of GLAM institutions and Digital Humanities (DH), as it has been a core theme from the outset. Today, this collaborative ethos is even more crucial due to the growing importance of data-driven research and interoperability. The efforts discussed so far introduce the immense work undertaken to transforming documents into data and developing shared solutions for qualifying, connecting, and creating new meanings from this content. In particular, we see how the idea of **Linked Open Data (LOD)** (Berners-Lee 2006) has been fundamental to laying the foundation for the so-called *Web of Data*. This concept represents a paradigm shift, enabling data to be openly shared and interconnected, ultimately leading to the creation of a **cultural heritage knowledge graph**, where entities held by different institutions are linked through a semantic layer.

³ <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/en/#iso:std:iso:8879:ed-1:v1:en>

⁴ <http://tei-c.org>

⁵ <https://www.w3.org/2001/sw/>

A prominent contemporary example of interoperability and the application of Linked Open Data principles in the GLAM sector is **Europeana**⁶, a digital platform launched by the European Union. Europeana aggregates metadata and digital objects from galleries, libraries, archives, and museums across Europe, to create a unified access point for cultural heritage. The platform operates on the principles of **interoperability**, enabling diverse institutions to both contribute and retrieve data through standardized metadata models like **EDM (Europeana Data Model)**, which is based on Semantic Web technologies such as RDF and OWL. By employing LOD principles, Europeana facilitates the interlinking of cultural heritage objects, allowing users to explore relationships between artworks, artifacts, and historical documents across institutions. Furthermore, Europeana demonstrates how the GLAM sector can transform traditional cataloging practices into a collaborative knowledge graph, embodying the ideals of open and linked data. This not only enhances discoverability and accessibility but also empowers institutions to use shared datasets for innovative research and educational initiatives.

As analyzed in this thesis, the GLAM sector is shifting towards increasingly open and interoperable models and investing in new analytical approaches to data to enhance knowledge discovery. In particular, this research examines existing methods for representing images, explores how annotations contribute to both the creation and discoverability of new data, and investigates the challenges associated with the usability of Linked Open Data (LOD) in cultural heritage contexts.

1.2 What is an Image in GLAM?

GLAM institutions engage with multiple media, and the concept of “cultural heritage” is broad and multifaceted. According to a 2014 UNESCO methodology manual, cultural heritage is defined as:

“[...] both a product and a process, which provides societies with a wealth of resources that are inherited from the past, created in the present, and bestowed for the benefit of future generations. Most importantly, it includes not only tangible but also natural and intangible heritage.” (UNESCO 2014)

This definition highlights the **layered nature of cultural heritage objects**, where tangible and intangible elements intertwine. It also underscores the breadth and complexity of the data generated by GLAM institutions, which span multiple disciplines and reflect diverse temporal, geographical, and cultural contexts.

⁶ <https://www.europeana.eu/>

This complexity is particularly evident in the case of visual objects. Visual objects not only document or represent tangible cultural artifacts but also serve as carriers of intangible dimensions, such as symbolic meaning, artistic interpretation, and historical context. A comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted nature of images is essential for their documentation, preservation, and accessibility within GLAM institutions. This chapter will examine the challenges and opportunities of representing visual objects, emphasizing how their layered meanings can be captured, structured, and shared through evolving technologies and methodologies.

1.2.1 Historical Context

The evolution of visual art spans from prehistoric cave drawings to contemporary semantic web, encompassing many historical transformations. Today, within the cultural heritage field, “image” often evokes the idea of a museum painting, especially within the Western context, where this form became prominent around the mid-15th century. Historically, however, visual art—from early cave pictograms to Renaissance religious paintings—was often associated with sacred spaces and not intended for public display. Temples, private residences, and tombs served as exclusive spaces for art for millennia.

Prior to the 19th century, when museums began to play a central role in collecting art, wealthy patrons primarily commissioned works for private enjoyment or exclusive audiences (McCarthy et al. 2005). By the 17th century, intellectual interest in human and natural history grew, leading to the formation of specialized collections by scholars and scientists. Prominent institutions such as the *Accademia del Cimento* (Florence, 1657), the *Royal Society* (London, 1660), and the *Académie des Sciences* (Paris, 1666) began organizing their collections with emerging classification systems, reflecting Europe’s shift toward rational inquiry and systematic knowledge.

The Enlightenment era brought the rise of **public museums**. The *Ashmolean Museum* at Oxford (1683) is often recognized as the first public museum established by a public institution. Other encyclopedic museums followed, including the *British Museum* (1759) in London, formed from private collections, and the *Louvre* (1793) in Paris, created by opening royal collections to the public (International Council of Museums 2006).

Today, the GLAM sector’s approach to “images” has significantly expanded. Institutions manage a wide variety of digital collection of images, and interoperability requires a broad perspective on what these images represent. For example, one institution may hold an **original artwork**, such as a framed canvas, while another may manage a **photographic archive** documenting the artwork, where the photograph itself becomes a distinct object with its own metadata. A third institution may house **related documents**, such as manuscripts, sketches, or commission notes linked to the artwork.

These multiple layers—original artwork, documentation, and contextual records—must be considered when developing a cohesive framework for working with images in DH projects. As a result, there is an ongoing effort to break down traditional silos of information across institutions, fostering a more interconnected and comprehensive understanding of cultural heritage.

Digital images, as unique information sources, often suffer from inefficient management due to their complexity, resulting in suboptimal search and retrieval processes. While various initiatives aim to improve image retrieval, significant gaps remain in the way images are represented, particularly in their contextual and semantic dimensions.

Currently, images are often described using **keywords**, which are subjective and rely on textual descriptions, or through **automatic extraction of visual features**. However, a comprehensive representation should combine both **visual content** and **non-visual metadata**, including author, modification date, format, etc. This dual approach improves image retrieval by considering both the content and context of the images.

The complexity of visual objects and their associated metadata necessitates structured models for their effective representation and management within CH institutions. Theoretical frameworks such as FRBR (now LRM) and its extensions provide a foundation for addressing these challenges.

1.2.2 Semantic Representation of Images

As previously mentioned, the representation of information in an image requires handling different layers or levels. Two primary paradigms stand out for image representation: **concept-based** and **content-based** (Roa-Martínez, Coneglian, and Vidotti 2023). In the **concept-based paradigm**, images are described with words or indexing. These practices involve some kind of manual description of the image and using a template to select the concepts representing the image. It is evident that this indexing process is inherently subjective due to human participation in the process and can be highly time-consuming when dealing with large collections. Conversely, the **content-based paradigm** relies on computational techniques from Digital Image Processing to automatically analyze features such as color, texture, and other elements that constitute the syntactic level of an image. While this type of syntactic indexing enables rapid processing of large quantities of files and reduces subjectivity, it poses challenges for semantic retrieval, as it focuses on physical attributes rather than the underlying meaning.

It is argued that the representation of images by concept can be further divided into **representation of visual content** and **representation of non-visual content**. The former deals with the elements within the image (iconographic and intrinsic) and verbal or textual descriptors (e.g., keywords or phrases). Non-visual content representation refers to information extrinsic to the image, which is not

present in the image itself but is related to it, such as metadata about its creator, date, or context of creation. Such extrinsic information is particularly valuable for improving retrieval processes.

Information Science approaches digital images by considering both their content and contextual information, while **Semantic Web Technologies (SWT)** significantly enhance image processing and representation. SWT, including ontologies and linked data systems, facilitate the semantic enrichment of images by structuring data according to established standards. This improves interoperability and enables computational systems to infer and more effectively address user needs. This is particularly crucial for image retrieval, where SWT can expand the system's capacity to process complex queries by integrating both visual and contextual elements.

Before analyzing the different levels of image readability, it is essential to understand the role of entities and layers in the CH field, along with their connection to the LOD paradigm. **Entities** form the cornerstone of the LOD structure, serving as subjects or objects within RDF triples that define relationships between resources. The Semantic Web stack organizes information hierarchically, transitioning from standardized string encoding to representational syntax and ultimately to semantic layers. These principles align closely with the FRBR framework, which has evolved beyond its bibliographic origins into a flexible standard for describing objects across various domains.

The **FRBR conceptual model** introduces the **WEMI** (Work, Expression, Manifestation, Item) structure, providing a framework for parsing cultural objects into four distinct layers. This conceptual model has been the result of a shift in perspective from traditional cataloging systems, moving the focus from compiling cataloging records to the identification of the nature of the informational content within those records. This reconceptualization laid the groundwork for structuring data to improve accessibility and retrieval (Tomasi 2022).

A notable extension of FRBR is **FRBRoo**, an object-oriented ontology aligned with **CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC-CRM)**⁷. FRBRoo, now **LRMoo**⁸, bridges libraries and museums by conceptualizing cultural heritage objects as dynamic, stratified processes. As outlined in its specifications:

“Libraries and museums are memory institutions – both strive to preserve cultural heritage objects and information about such objects, and they often share the same users. Besides, the boundary between them is often blurred: libraries hold several museum objects and museums hold several library objects; the

⁷ <https://cidoc-crm.org/>

⁸ <https://cidoc-crm.org/lrmoo/>

cultural heritage objects preserved in both types of institutions were created in the same cultural context or period, sometimes by the same agents, and they provide evidence of comparable cultural features. It seems therefore appropriate to build a common conceptualization of the information gathered by the two types of organizations about cultural heritage.” (Bekiari et al. 2015, 13)

This approach is particularly relevant for representing visual objects, allowing GLAM institutions to describe digital collections as dynamic and multi-layered entities that integrate intrinsic characteristics with contextual relationships.

Introduced in 1998, FRBR established a foundation for conceptualizing bibliographic data through the WEMI model. However, challenges related to harmonization and redundancy arose as FRBR evolved alongside its related models—**FRAD (Functional Requirements for Authority Data)** and **FRSAD (Functional Requirements for Subject Authority Data)**. To address these issues, the **IFLA Library Reference Model (LRM)** was introduced in 2017.

LRM consolidates FRBR, FRAD, and FRSAD into a unified framework, retaining core concepts like WEMI while incorporating new entities such as **Agent**, **Place**, and **Time-span** to improve versatility in both bibliographic and Semantic Web applications. This evolution has also influenced the object-oriented ontology extension of FRBR, now revised as LRMoo, which continues to align with CIDOC-CRM while adapting to the refined concepts of LRM. These developments collectively represent a broader effort to unify bibliographic standards, enhancing their applicability for linked data ecosystems and emerging technological contexts.

Integration of Interpretive Models

Theoretical frameworks for the formal analysis of images often classify the types of content and information found in digital images. Among these, **Panofsky's Iconographic Model** is one of the most influential (Kalkanis 2018). This model will be further explored in following section, for now, it is useful to note it divides the image representation into three distinct levels: (1) identification of objects within the image based on visual primitives such as color and shape, without interpretation; (2) recognition of themes and concepts, which require interpretative effort; and (3) intrinsic meaning of the image, which involves a higher degree of semantic inference and contextual knowledge from scholars.

Similarly, **Shatford's framework** expands on Panofsky's model, maintaining three levels of description while incorporating four additional facets at each level: *who*, *what*, *where*, and *when*. It also accounts for external, non-visual information categorized as bibliographical, exemplified, and related data (Shatford 1986).

Another notable framework, **Jaimes and Chang’s model**, introduces ten levels of visual description, classified into two main categories: syntactic-perceptual and semantic-conceptual. It also considers non-visual, contextual information related to the historical and biographical aspects of the image (Jaimes and Chang 1999, 2–15).

Collectively, these models highlight the importance of representing both syntactic and semantic content of images, as well as non-visual or extrinsic information. Non-visual elements, such as image format, author, date, location, or lighting conditions, play a crucial role in image retrieval and in uncovering new knowledge. It is essential to recognize that the representation of digital images must account for both syntactic and semantic visual content, as well as non-visual information. Representing the multiple layers of an image can significantly enhance retrieval processes, with SWT playing a crucial role in this effort.

In the context of the Semantic Web, where computational agents can identify concepts and process information and possible meanings, the textual representation of the information contained within a visual document and its context is particularly significant, as it allows the knowledge embedded in images to be made explicit. This explicit description enables machines to understand the information, ensuring it is interoperable and accessible across various formats. SWT provides mechanisms for representing both the syntactic and semantic aspects of a resource while enabling the creation, storage, manipulation, and processing of non-visual image information. For instance, as highlighted in a proceeding paper by Bannour and Hudelot (2011), the use of ontologies in the field of **image retrieval** serves to unify the description of low-level features and represent the various relationships between image characteristics through ontologies of visual description. Furthermore, ontologies facilitate the alignment of the visual level with the semantic level via semantic mapping. Structured metadata enables datasets to interlink with authority records such as the **Virtual International Authority File (VIAF)**⁹ and general-purpose knowledge bases like **DBpedia**¹⁰, fostering enriched contextualization and interoperability.

Levels of interpretation

As established, images convey information on multiple levels. In the CH domain, various frameworks and experimental methodologies have been developed to provide nuanced descriptions of specific image types, such as artworks. Defining what constitutes an “artwork” remains challenging, however, a widely accepted definition describes it as:

⁹ <https://viaf.org/>

¹⁰ <https://www.dbpedia.org/>

“[...] visual object or experience consciously created through an expression of skill or imagination [...]” (Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica 2020)

A conceptual reference models designed to standardize and integrate cultural heritage information across institutions, such as CIDOC-CRM, addresses the complexities of describing artwork by modeling assertions about objects through classes like `E13_Attribute_Assignment`, which formalize the connection between the assertion made by an agent and the object under consideration. Similarly, the **ArCo ontology** (Carriero et al. 2019), developed for modeling Italian cultural heritage artifacts, introduces the class `Interpretation`, which formalizes all information asserted by an agent about an object, encompassing measurements and scientific observations. The CIDOC-CRM extensions **CRMinf**¹¹ (for inference logic) and **CRMsci**¹² (for scientific reasoning) extend this framework by formalizing shared scientific process and activities across different domains. CRMsci, in particular, provides a structured approach to modeling scientific observations, data collection, and hypothesis formulation in cultural heritage and scientific documentation. For example, the class `crmsci:S4_Observation`—a subclass of `crmsci:I1_Argumentation` and `crm:E13_Attribute_Assignment`—models the process of scientific observation of physical events or phenomena, whether directly or through instrument-based measurements. This class represents the transition between empirical reality and formalized propositions, enabling structured documentation of observational data and its interpretation (Doerr et al. 2014). The **VIR ontology**¹³ further refines this conceptualization by introducing the subclass `vir:IC12_Representation`, which assigns an exclusively iconographical status to a physical object. This innovation allows for the precise modeling of an object’s visual characteristics and its interpretation within an iconographical framework.

Historical and Multi-Perspectival Interpretations

In the historical domain, conflicting interpretations often arise, as historians provide different perspectives on the same events. Ontologies such as **SEM (Simple Event Model)**¹⁴, **MIDM (Multiple Interpretation Data Model)** (Van Ruymbeke et al. 2018), and **Event-Model-F** (an extension DOLCE+DnS Ultralite) (Scherp et al. 2009) address this challenge by modeling varying interpretations of the same event (Frank 2019). SEM facilitates the representation of multiple viewpoints by linking events to their asserting agents, thereby capturing diverse perspectives. MIDM facilitates the modeling of diverse interpretations of historical events by distinguishing between the

¹¹ <https://cidoc-crm.org/crminf>

¹² <https://cidoc-crm.org/crmsci>

¹³ <https://ncarboni.github.io/vir/>

¹⁴ <https://semanticweb.cs.vu.nl/2009/11/sem/>

representation of historical reality and the knowledge about it, allowing different viewpoints to coexist within structured representations. Event-Model-F builds upon DOLCE+DnS Ultralite to provide a comprehensive framework for representing events, including their temporal and spatial dimensions, participants, and relationships, supporting the integration of multiple perspectives and contextual information (Scherp et al. 2009). Within these frameworks, a distinction is made between "facts" and "interpretations," emphasizing how differing viewpoints can coexist in structured representations. Ontologies like DOLCE+DnS Ultralite, utilized in Event-Model-F, employ constructs such as "descriptions" and "situations" to differentiate between objective occurrences (facts) and the contextual interpretations or perspectives of those occurrences (Gangemi and Mika 2003).

Among these models, the **HiCO Ontology (Historical Context Ontology)**¹⁵ (Daquino and Tomasi 2015) is particularly notable for its capacity to add contextual layers to interpretations. HiCO centers on the interpretation act, a fundamental process for extracting meaningful RDF statements from cultural heritage objects. Each interpretation act is linked to an agent (e.g., a scholar or system) and formalize the subjective process of deriving context-specific knowledge from a cultural object. HiCO formalizes these relationships through object properties from **PROV-O**¹⁶ and **FRBR models**, ensuring a clear connection between interpretative acts and the cultural object they analyze.

For instance, interpretations are linked to the *Expression* entity of a cultural object's *Work* (via `hico:isExtractedFrom`) and documented as being generated by an interpretative act (`prov:wasGeneratedBy`). This structure highlights the interpretative layer as distinct from the object itself, emphasizing the subjective nature of the process.

HiCO also defines key properties, including `hico:hasInterpretationType` and `hico:hasInterpretationCriterion`, to further classify interpretations. These properties enable the classification of the interpretation's nature (e.g., philological, historical, linguistic) and the methods or criteria applied (e.g., transcription, hypothesis formulation, or reliance on secondary literature). These properties enhance transparency of the interpretative process and facilitate the evaluation of authority and reliability. Additionally, HiCO reuses existing ontologies, such as **CiTO (Citation Typing Ontology)**¹⁷, to establish links between attributions to related sources, thereby enhancing the credibility of assertions through supporting evidence. For instance, a philological interpretation

¹⁵ <http://purl.org/emmedi/hico>

¹⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

¹⁷ <https://sparontologies.github.io/cito/current/cito.html>

identifying a historical figure can be cross-referenced with other interpretations derived from the same or related sources, thereby forming a cohesive web of evidence.

Adding further complexity to the discussion of interpretative layers, the **MIMA (Multi-disciplinary Interpretations Model on Manuscript Apparatus)**¹⁸ offers a robust framework for representing scholars' multidisciplinary analyses of the same artifact (Daquino, Pasqual, and Tomasi 2020). MIMA organizes interpretative layers into four distinct levels:

- **Level 0:** Factual data, non-questionable, objective metadata.
- **Level 1:** Assertions and data subject to interpretation, such as non-universally accepted declarations.
- **Level 2:** Context of the assertion, including provenance, certainty, type and criteria of interpretation, sources, and authorship.
- **Level 3:** Context of the publication of statements, including authorship and timing.

When integrated with the FRBR's WEMI structure, MIMA demonstrates how interpretative layers can be systematically applied to specific components of an artifact, particularly its *Expression* and *Manifestation*. This integration facilitates a nuanced representation of cultural heritage objects, accommodating various scholarly perspectives.

ICON: Translating Panofsky's Framework

An important DH project that advances the interpretation of images is the ontology **ICON**¹⁹ (Sartini et al. 2023). This ontology is directly inspired by the work of the German art historian Erwin Panofsky and his influential iconographical-iconological method, previously introduced in this thesis. ICON defines classes and properties to express artistic interpretations of figurative artworks' subject matter (iconographies) and meanings (symbols, iconological aspects). The goal of this ontology is to provide scholars with a structured tool for expressing iconographic and iconological statements with the appropriate level of granularity. This is essential because interpreting culture objects—especially images—requires an understanding that goes beyond their physical appearance. Images often act as carriers of semantic meaning, making the process of interpretation a critical aspect of working with them in cultural heritage contexts. ICON is designed for use by three primary audiences: 1) museums, aiming to describe artworks in greater depth; 2) art historians, conducting research that integrates qualitative and quantitative methodologies; 3) developers, particularly in computer vision, seeking to associate content descriptions with portions of artworks.

¹⁸ <https://mima-data-model.github.io/mima-documentation/>

¹⁹ <https://br0ast.github.io/ICON/ICONOntologyDocumentationcurrent/index-en.html>

The interpretation of an artwork or image is inherently tied to the observer's background knowledge. The depth of understanding depends on how familiar the observer is with the artist, stylistic conventions, and the cultural context in which the work was created. The more knowledge the observer brings, the more accurate their interpretation at each level becomes, enabling deeper insights into the artwork's cultural, historical, and ideological significance.

Structurally, ICON is grounded in Panofsky's interpretative framework, as described in *Studies in Iconology* (1939). Panofsky's model subdivides the interpretation of images into three levels, which ICON formally represents in an ontological schema:

- **Pre-iconographical Description:** This is the most basic level of interpretation, involving the straightforward identification of shapes, figures, and forms in an image. At this stage, there is no interpretation of meaning, only the recognition of visually present elements. For instance, identifying a figure as a child or recognizing an object as a tree.
- **Iconographical Analysis:** The second level involves interpreting the elements identified in the first level as representations of specific themes, symbols, or narratives. For example, recognizing a figure as Cupid. This level requires some contextual knowledge, such as familiarity with mythology, religious symbols, or historical motifs.
- **Iconological Interpretation:** The third and most complex level situates the image within its broader cultural and historical context to uncover deeper meanings. This involves analyzing the societal values, ideologies, and cultural narratives that the image reflects. For example, a depiction of Cupid might not only symbolize love but also convey the Renaissance's philosophical ideals or a particular patron's intentions when commissioning the artwork.

The ICON ontology represents a significant step in formalizing Erwin Panofsky's influential iconographic-iconological method into a machine-readable framework. By translating Panofsky's three levels of interpretation—pre-iconographical, iconographical, and iconological—into structured ontological classes, ICON provides a scholarly tool for the semantic representation of artworks. To demonstrate its capabilities, the ontology has been applied in two major datasets: ICONdataset²⁰ and IICONGRAPH²¹ (Sartini 2024), which illustrate its potential for advancing art historical research through LOD principles.

²⁰ <https://w3id.org/icon/data/>

²¹ <https://github.com/br0ast/iicongraph/>

ICONdataset is a manually annotated knowledge graph containing over 5,500 art historians' interpretations related to more than 400 artworks. As key feature of the dataset used to apply the ICON model we can see:

- **Structured Representation:** CIDOC-CRM and ICON ontologies model intricate relationships between artworks, interpretations, art historians, and their sources. These relationships are classified by properties like `icon:hasRecognition` and detailed further through `icon:recognizedIntrinsicMeaning` and `icon:hasFactualMeaning`.
- **Art Historians and Provenance:** The dataset includes detailed information about art historians such as Erwin Panofsky, linking their interpretations to specific artworks. These connections provide a foundation for assessing the scholarly reliability of each recognition.
- **Citations and Bibliographic Connections:** Recognitions are linked to bibliographic resources via the `cito:citesForInformation` property, enabling users to trace the scholarly works that inform interpretations. For example, the interpretation of the Titian's artwork "*Sacred and Profane Love*" is connected to WorldCat entries for its bibliographic data.

While the manual compilation approach employed in ICONdataset ensures high accuracy and scholarly oversight, its time-consuming nature limits scalability, as reflected in the relatively modest number of artworks and interpretations it covers.

In contrast to the ICONdataset, IICONGRAPH adopts a semi-automatic approach to constructing its knowledge graph. This methodology enables the incorporation of a much larger dataset, significantly expanding the quantity of artworks and interpretations while maintaining alignment with the ICON ontology. Key Innovations of IICONGRAPH are:

- **Semi-Automatic Knowledge Graph Construction:** IICONGRAPH integrates iconographic and iconological statements from Wikidata and ArCo, re-engineering these datasets according to the ICON ontology structure. This approach balances scalability with semantic depth, enabling the inclusion of a broader range of interpretations.
- **Integration of HyperReal Enrichment:** By incorporating data from the HyperReal knowledge graph, IICONGRAPH introduces an additional layer of symbolic enrichment. HyperReal contains over 40,000 instances of symbolism, linking symbols (e.g., a cat) to their cultural meanings (e.g., divinity in Egyptian contexts) based on sources like symbol dictionaries and encyclopedias. This enrichment enhances the graph's ability to address complex questions about cultural symbolism.
- **Interoperability and FAIR Principles:** IICONGRAPH adheres to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). Persistent URIs are provided through the

w3id service (e.g., <https://w3id.org/iiconograph/data/>) for datasets, documentation, and case studies. The knowledge graph is hosted on Zenodo and accessible via its DOI²².

- Shortcuts in ICON Ontology Version 2.0: The updated ICON ontology includes shortcuts that directly link an artwork to its pre-iconographical, iconographical, or iconological elements. These enhancements simplify queries and improve accessibility for both human and computational agents.

Modeling Images and Attribution

The challenges of modeling images in the CH domain extend beyond the technical aspects of representation, encompassing issues of authoritativeness and reliability in data sources. As highlighted by Daquino's work on art historical Linked Data, attributions often involve conflicting interpretations and a lack of formalized criteria for assessing reliability (Daquino 2019). Her research demonstrates how Semantic Web technologies and Information Quality measures can address these challenges by combining data analysis with domain expertise.

Daquino's conceptual framework leverages Information Quality (IQ) metrics to rank the authoritativeness of secondary sources, providing a reproducible approach for validating attributions. This framework integrates textual and cognitive authority, with the latter offering insights into the credibility of scholars and data providers. The study underscores the potential of semantic modeling not only to enhance metadata quality but also to reveal biases and inconsistencies in attribution practices.

Future directions outlined in her work align with the broader goals of this thesis, emphasizing the importance of interdisciplinary methodologies and scalable solutions for integrating interpretive and semantic layers. By building on such frameworks, the modeling of images can evolve to support richer, more reliable representations, enabling both scholarly and computational agents to engage with cultural heritage data more effectively.

1.3 International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF)

After analyzing the conceptual models of images in the GLAM sector, we now examine one of the most prominent frameworks for image delivery and visualization: the **International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF** – pronounced “triple-eye-eff”)²³. In this section, we explore IIIF's specifications and design principles, providing an essential technological overview to

²² <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10294588>

²³ <https://iiif.io/>

contextualize its role within GLAM institutions, particularly in relation to images, annotations, and data usability, which are central to this research.

IIIF originated as a model for presenting and annotating digital content. While its initial focus was on images, the framework has since evolved to support the delivery and annotation of video and audio content. A fundamental aspect of IIIF is its community-driven approach. More than just a technical specification, IIIF represents a global network of institutions and individuals committed to developing and maintaining shared APIs, implementing them in software, and exposing interoperable content. This diverse community includes institutions such as national and state libraries (e.g., the *Vatican Library* and the *British Library*), archives (e.g., the *Swiss Federal Archives* and the *Internet Archive*), museums and galleries (e.g., the *J. Paul Getty Trust*, the *Smithsonian Institution*, and the *MIT Museum*), universities and research institutions (e.g., *Cambridge*, *Yale*, and *Oxford*), and aggregators like *Europeana*. The IIIF community is organized into groups that regularly convene to discuss both technical and non-technical aspects of IIIF's development and implementation. A detailed schedule of IIIF group calls, typically held via Zoom, is available on the official website²⁴.

True to its name, IIIF's primary goal is to promote interoperability in the delivery and interaction with images and audio/visual content. The framework defines a **set of standardized APIs** that enable consistent methods for delivering digital content from servers to various online environments. These APIs also facilitate the inclusion of structural metadata, allowing for **interactive exploration** and **sequential viewing of images**. Beyond basic viewing functionalities, IIIF supports advanced features such as: **deep zoom**, enabling detailed examination of high-resolution images; **image comparison**, allowing scholars and researchers to juxtapose multiple digital objects; **organization of digital objects into meaningful structures**, such as maintaining the page order of digitized books. Additionally, it supports **annotations**, making it a versatile tool for working with cultural heritage materials.

At the core of the IIIF standard are two key components (see Figure 1):

1. The **Image API**, which enables the efficient retrieval and manipulation of images, allowing users to request specific regions, sizes, rotations, and formats.
2. The **Presentation API**, which facilitates the structured display and interaction with digital objects by defining manifests that provide metadata about sequences, structures, and relationships between images.

²⁴ <https://iiif.io/community/>

By establishing clear protocols and specifications, IIIF ensures that various systems and applications can uniformly interpret and interact with digital resources, thereby fostering interoperability across platforms.

Figure 1 - A diagram of how the core IIIF APIs work together. (Source: <https://iiif.io/get-started/how-iiif-works/>)

This interoperability is further strengthened by IIIF’s collaborative design process. Cultural heritage institutions, libraries, museums, archives, and technology experts actively contribute to the ongoing development and refinement of the framework, ensuring that it remains robust, inclusive, and adaptable to diverse domains. Such collaboration is critical for establishing a standardized, shared environment that meets the needs of various stakeholders while supporting sustainable access and engagement with digital cultural heritage materials.

1.3.1 Image API 3.0

The Image API²⁵ is the first of the two core IIIF’s APIs. It is a RESTful API which defines rules and methods for image servers to transmit image pixels to a viewer. It provides flexibility by enabling images to be delivered in various configurations, such as full-sized images, resized versions, zoomed-in portions, or black-and-white renditions. These configurations are controlled by modifying segments of the URI associated with the Image API resource. To experiment with these features, a dedicated testing tool is available at: <https://www.learniiif.org/image-api/playground>. The code below shows how the URI of the image is composed:

```
{scheme}://{server}/{prefix}/{identifier}/{region}/{size}/{rotation}/{quality}.{format}
```

²⁵ <https://iiif.io/api/image/3.0/>

The Image API can function independently, frequently used for functionalities like rapid, deep zooming on high-resolution files (e.g., TIFF or JPEG2000 formats). Alternatively, it integrates seamlessly with the Presentation API to enhance viewing capabilities.

1.3.2 Presentation API 3.0

While Image API governs the delivery and transformation of image resources, the **Presentation API**²⁶ structures the contextual information necessary for viewing and interacting with digital objects. This API enhances digital objects by attaching **essential metadata** and **structural information**, dictating their appearance in IIIF-compatible viewers. At the core of the Presentation API is the **Manifest**, a **JSON file** that consolidates all components of an IIIF object, including metadata and hierarchical structure (e.g., page order for digitized books). Both digitized physical objects and born-digital content benefit from a standardized description, which defines their layout and presentation mode. The primary function of the Presentation API is to aggregate and structure digital objects for human consumption, working in conjunction with the Image API. However, it is important to note that this descriptive information is intended for human readability, not for machine interpretation. As explicitly stated in the IIIF documentation for the latest API version: “[...] *it explicitly does not aim to provide metadata that allow a search engine to index digital objects*”. While it is recommended further exploration of the official IIIF documentation, it is valuable to describe the core model used to structure compound objects (via the Manifest resource) and their individual views (via Canvas resources). The following section provides an overview of the resource types (or classes) defined in the Presentation API specification (see Figure 2).

²⁶ <https://iiif.io/api/presentation/3.0/>

Figure 2 - IIIF Presentation API 3.0 Data Model. (Source: <https://iiif.io/api/presentation/3.0/>)

Collection

A **Collection** organizes and sequences **Manifests** and/or additional **Collections** into a hierarchical structure. It facilitates navigation, dynamic search results, and the grouping of related resources. For instance, a Collection might include multiple Manifests representing volumes in a multi-volume work or group related artworks from a single artist.

Purposes:

- Enable navigation through large datasets.
- Represent logical or thematic groupings of resources.
- Aggregate resources for presentation or discovery.

Manifest

The **Manifest** is the most critical resource in the Presentation API, providing a detailed **JSON-LD (JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data)**²⁷ description of a compound object. It consolidates all elements necessary to display the object in a IIIF viewer, including **metadata**, **structure**, and **links to external resources**.

²⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/json-ld11/>

Below is a JSON-LD Manifest example for a digitized two-page book, illustrating key features such as multilingual metadata, linked external data, and structural hierarchy.

```
{
  "@context": "http://iiif.io/api/presentation/3/context.json",
  "id": "https://example.org/iiif/book/manifest.json",
  "type": "Manifest",
  "label": {
    "en": [ "Two-Page Book" ],
    "it": [ "Libro a Due Pagine" ]
  },
  "metadata": [
    {
      "label": { "en": [ "Author" ], "it": [ "Autore" ] },
      "value": { "en": [ "Jane Doe" ], "it": [ "Jane Doe" ] }
    },
    {
      "label": { "en": [ "Date" ], "it": [ "Data" ] },
      "value": { "en": [ "2024" ], "it": [ "2024" ] }
    }
  ],
  "behavior": [ "paged" ],
  "seeAlso": [
    {
      "id": "https://example.org/iiif/book/metadata.xml",
      "type": "Dataset",
      "format": "application/xml",
      "profile": "http://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/"
    }
  ],
  "items": [
    {
      "id": "https://example.org/iiif/book/canvas/page1",
      "type": "Canvas",
      "label": {
        "en": [ "Page 1" ],
        "it": [ "Pagina 1" ]
      },
      "width": 1500,
      "height": 2000,
      "items": [
        {
          "id": "https://example.org/iiif/book/canvas/page1/image",
          "type": "Annotation",
          "motivation": "painting",
          "body": {
            "id": "https://example.org/images/page1.jpg",
            "type": "Image",
            "format": "image/jpeg",
            "width": 1500,
            "height": 2000
          },
          "target": "https://example.org/iiif/book/canvas/page1"
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

```

    ]
  },
  {
    "id": "https://example.org/iiif/book/canvas/page2",
    "type": "Canvas",
    "label": {
      "en": [ "Page 2" ],
      "it": [ "Pagina 2" ]
    },
    "width": 1500,
    "height": 2000,
    "items": [
      {
        "id": "https://example.org/iiif/book/canvas/page2/image",
        "type": "Annotation",
        "motivation": "painting",
        "body": {
          "id": "https://example.org/images/page2.jpg",
          "type": "Image",
          "format": "image/jpeg",
          "width": 1500,
          "height": 2000
        },
        "target": "https://example.org/iiif/book/canvas/page2"
      }
    ]
  }
]
}

```

Let's highlight the different sections of the JSON above.

The `@context` property defines the JSON-LD context for interpreting the manifest. By pointing to `"http://iiif.io/api/presentation/3/context.json"`, it ensures that the data structure aligns with IIIF Presentation API 3.0 specifications. This context enables the JSON document to be understood as a linked data graph.

The `id` property uniquely identifies the Manifest (`"https://example.org/iiif/book/manifest.json"` in the example). Combined with the `type` property, set to `"Manifest"`, it designates the resource as a IIIF Manifest. This uniqueness is crucial for referencing and sharing the Manifest across platforms.

The `label` property provides a human-readable title or name for the Manifest. It supports multilingual capabilities, as demonstrated by the `"en"` (English) and `"it"` (Italian) labels. This feature ensures accessibility for a global audience and highlights IIIF's commitment to inclusivity.

Metadata offers descriptive information about the object, such as its title, date, or creator. It is represented as an array of key-value pairs, with `label` for the metadata title and value for the

associated information. The multilingual structure of metadata mirrors that of label, allowing institutions to present content in multiple languages.

The "behavior": ["paged"] property defines the intended viewing behavior of the digital object. The paged value specifies that the resource (e.g., a book) should be presented as a two-page spread, mimicking the experience of reading a physical book.

The seeAlso property enables links to external metadata resources, such as Dublin Core²⁸ or MARC records, significantly enhancing the Manifest's semantic richness by connecting it to additional structured information. IIF adopts a content-agnostic approach, prioritizing content delivery rather than enforcing specific semantic interpretations (Raemy and Demleitner 2023). The seeAlso property bridges this gap by allowing institutions to link external metadata resources that can convey the semantic context of the content. For instance, a digitized manuscript can link to its authoritative catalog entry or related bibliographic datasets, enabling seamless access to supplementary data while respecting IIF's content-agnostic philosophy.

Annotations within IIF Manifests serve a dual purpose. They render images onto the Canvas while adhering to the **Web Annotation Data Model (WADM)**²⁹. For instance, the "motivation": "painting" property explicitly identifies the annotation's role in rendering visual content. The body property contains the image resource, including its URL (id), format (image/jpeg), and dimensions. The target property connects this resource to the Canvas where it is displayed. This approach distinguishes IIF's use of annotations from traditional commentary or tagging functions, emphasizing its role in delivering content seamlessly.

Canvas

A Canvas is a virtual container that represents a specific view of a digital object, serving as a framework for content layout, both spatially and temporally. The Canvas model is inspired by formats such as PDF and HTML, as well as applications like Photoshop and PowerPoint, where a blank surface progressively accumulates images, video, text, and other content through Annotations, which are organized in Annotation Pages. The Canvas plays a pivotal role in this research, particularly in enabling the integration of dislocated manuscript fragments from different institutions into a unified view. This functionality exemplifies IIF's potential to facilitate cross-institutional collaboration and comprehensive visualizations. For example, it is common for parts of the same manuscript to be held by different institutions, particularly in the case of illuminated manuscripts. The "*Châteauroux*

²⁸ <https://www.dublincore.org/>

²⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/annotation-model/>

*manuscript demo*³⁰ provides a clear example of this phenomenon. With IIIF Canvas, these separate parts can be represented in the same unified view, allowing multiple Canvases to be assembled within a single representation.

Range

A Range is an organized compilation of Canvases and/or additional Ranges. It allows for the grouping of Canvases in a meaningful way, based on content-related structures (e.g., a table of contents or scenes in a play) or physical characteristics (e.g., page gatherings in early books or the arrangement of recorded music across multiple physical carriers, such as CDs).

For the purposes of this research, it is essential to highlight several additional types defined within WADM, which are integral to the IIIF Presentation API. These types extend the functionality of annotations and facilitate sophisticated interactions with digital objects.

Annotation Page

An Annotation Page is a sequenced collection of annotations, typically linked to a Canvas but also capable of referencing other types of resources. Annotation Pages systematically organize and arrange annotations, allowing for insights, comments, or other forms of interaction with the content associated with a Canvas. This structure is particularly crucial for handling multiple annotations in a coherent, accessible, and scalable way, especially when dealing with complex digital resources.

Annotation

Annotations establish associations between content resources and Canvases. They provide a unified mechanism to connect visible and audible resources, as well as transcriptions, commentary, tags, or other supplementary content. This flexibility enhances collaboration, allowing distributed systems to align content descriptions with those created by other institutions. IIIF Annotations follow the Web Annotation Data Model and may include additional specialized classes, such as:

- **SpecificResource**: defines a precisely targeted annotation within a resource.
- **Choice**: enables conditional or alternative annotations, allowing different content variations.
- **Selector**: allows fine-grained annotation targeting, specifying precise segments of text, images, or audiovisual content.

This extensibility makes annotations a cornerstone of IIIF's semantic interoperability.

³⁰ <https://demos.biblissima.fr/chateauroux/demo/>

Content

Content encompasses web resources, such as images, audio, video, and text, that are linked to a Canvas through annotations. These resources provide visual or auditory representations of annotated objects, forming the basis for rendering and presenting digital materials.

Annotation Collection

An Annotation Collection is a higher-level construct that groups Annotation Pages into a structured entity. This structure enables the organization of annotations into meaningful categories or themes. For example, an Annotation Collection might group English translations of a medieval French document separately from its transcriptions or modern French editions. Similarly, it can differentiate between a film's director's commentary and its script, offering a clear separation of content types while preserving context.

1.3.3 Other IIIF APIs

In addition to the Image API and Presentation API, IIIF provides a suite of additional APIs that enhance its functionality, interoperability and user experience. These APIs enable advanced features, ensuring that digital resources are not only accessible but also dynamic, secure, and easily shareable:

- **Content Search API:** This API introduces powerful search capabilities within IIIF resources, enabling users to locate specific text or metadata embedded in a Manifest. For example, institutions like the *British Library* use the Content Search API to enable keyword searches within digitized newspapers and manuscripts³¹. This functionality is crucial for enhancing discoverability in large collections and makes IIIF resources more accessible to researchers.
- **Authentication API:** Secure access to sensitive or restricted resources is made possible through this API, which supports login mechanisms and differential access control, ensuring restricted content is available only to authorized users while maintaining a smooth user experience. This is particularly important for institutions that manage copyright-protected or private collection.
- **Content State API:** The ability to generate sharable links to specific views of a resource is facilitated by this API. By capturing and representing a “state” of the viewer, including zoom levels, annotations, or specific Canvases, the API enables precise references.
- **Change Discovery API:** This API allows for the tracking and harvesting of updated to IIIF resources. This API is crucial for dynamic collections, enabling systems to detect and

³¹ <https://blogs.bl.uk/digital-scholarship/2017/11/crowdsourcing-using-iiif-and-web-annotations.html>

synchronize changes such as new content additions, metadata updates, or modifications to existing resources.

Together, these APIs form a comprehensive toolkit for creating, managing, and interacting with IIIF resources. They address critical challenges in modern digital scholarship, from ensuring secure access to enabling collaboration and maintaining synchronization.

1.3.4 IIIF viewers

IIIF viewers play a critical role in interpreting and displaying data retrieved from the IIIF Image and Presentation APIs. These client-side software applications interpret IIIF Manifests, providing user-friendly interfaces for exploring and interacting with digital resources. A Manifest, for instance, can be read by various viewers, including *Mirador*, *Universal Viewer*, *Clover*, *Glycerine Viewer*, and *Theseus*, among others³². Each viewer brings distinct features, catering to specific institutional or research-specific needs, while adhering to IIIF standards. To qualify as a IIIF-compliant viewer, tools must support the IIIF Presentation API version 3.0, offer a public instance that accepts `iiif-content` parameters from the Content State API, and demonstrate compatibility with at least one IIIF Cookbook recipe³³.

The Cookbook Recipe Matrix³⁴ offers a comprehensive overview of supported features for each viewer, assisting developers and institutions in selecting the most appropriate tool for their needs. Below are descriptions of some prominent IIIF viewers, each designed for specific use cases.

Mirador

Developed by *Harvard University*, **Mirador**³⁵ is one of the most versatile and widely adopted IIIF viewers. The latest version is Mirador 3, and it has been released in 2020 and it's a configurable and extensible IIIF viewer, it is an open-source JavaScript library that aims to provide comparison, visualization, annotate and analysis tools for IIIF content. The delivered package size of the new version is 64% reduced in size compared to version 2 and it is possible to install it via npm and yarn. Comparison and deep zoom, thanks to *Openseadragon*³⁶, still keys feature of this viewer. A key new development in the field of user experience is the possibility to manage windows independently, this means that it is possible to display more images at the same time and the windows are easy

³² <https://github.com/IIIF/awesome-iiif?tab=readme-ov-file#iiif-viewers>

³³ <https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/>

³⁴ <https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/matrix/>

³⁵ <https://projectmirador.org/>

³⁶ <https://openseadragon.github.io/>

arrangeable via dragging them with the mouse. New window tool allows to display the images in the manifest also as grid, allowing navigation of them via thumbnail. But the most important feature to the purpose of the research is the possibility to annotate the image and to draw the area on the image itself, using the plugin **Mirador Annotations**³⁷. The Search API is now fully supported, enabling users to search for annotations within an image. Additionally, all windows and panels in the UI are resizable and repositionable, allowing users to simultaneously view metadata and transcription for enhanced usability. Mirador also supports Canvas-level metadata display and is compatible with the IIF Auth API, ensuring secure access to restricted resources. Furthermore, Mirador's modular architecture allows for plug-in extensions, providing a highly customizable environment that offers significant opportunities for developers. In terms of visualization capabilities, IIF layers are fully supported, with options to adjust opacity and manage layer visibility, facilitating a more flexible and tailored viewing experience for digital image collections.

Universal Viewer

The **Universal Viewer**³⁸ is another prominent tool, valued for its multimedia capabilities and flexibility. In addition to rendering IIF Manifests, the Universal Viewer supports diverse media formats, including 3D models, audio, video, and PDFs. Its customizable interface enables institutions to tailor the viewer to their specific needs, while features like deep zoom, internationalization, embedded search functionality, and support for thematic customization ensure its broad applicability. Researchers benefit from its ability to embed deep links to specific pages or regions, enhancing usability for scholarly and public audiences.

Clover IIF

Clover IIF³⁹ offers a modular approach to IIF integration, designed as a user interface (UI) component library rather than a standalone viewer. Built with accessibility and developer experience in mind, Clover allows users to create custom IIF web interfaces that fully utilize the Presentation API. By breaking away from the traditional “viewer” paradigm, Clover supports the representation of any digital object—not just images. This flexibility makes it an excellent choice for developers seeking to embed IIF Presentation API capabilities within complex digital platforms or bespoke applications.

Glycerine Viewer

³⁷ <https://github.com/ProjectMirador/mirador-annotations>

³⁸ <https://universalviewer.io/>

³⁹ <https://samvera-labs.github.io/clover-iif>

The **Glycerine Viewer**⁴⁰ takes a specialized approach by integrating robust annotation features, making it particularly useful for researchers and institutions prioritizing annotation workflows. Originally designed for **Glycerine Workbench**⁴¹, the Viewer now supports IIF Manifests and annotations built with other tools, leveraging a modern Vue 3 framework. Glycerine Image Annotation Workbench enhances this offering by enabling researchers to create semantically enriched annotations, combining domain-specific vocabularies with critical analysis references. The platform fosters collaborative research by allowing annotations to be shared and published across institutional repositories, turning annotated images into research outputs. With its focus on annotation features and publishing workflows, Glycerine provides unmatched capabilities in the IIF ecosystem for detailed image analysis and scholarly collaboration.

⁴⁰ <https://github.com/Systemik-Solutions/glycerine-viewer>

⁴¹ <https://glycerine.io/workbench/>

2. Annotations and Semantic Web

Annotations are a fundamental scholarly tool, serving as a hermeneutical activity deeply rooted in the intellectual tradition. Historically, annotations were mainly associated with biblical studies, exegesis, and philology, but they are equally relevant in informal settings where they serve to contextualize, explain, comment on, or provide additional information about a text or other types of data. In the humanities, annotation is considered a “scholarly primitive”, as noted by John Unsworth (2000), who classifies it as one of the **foundational methods** that researchers use across disciplines and have multiple purposes, functioning as **informal comments** that act as reminders or organizers of the scholar workflow or as **semantic links** between different research materials, creating connections between an edited text and other elements, such as another text or an image. As highlighted by Peter Boot (2009), annotations create a “dialogic structure” by explicitly connecting a passage of text or an image to its translation, explanation, or artifact. This process situates the annotated object within a specific intellectual or cultural context, providing insights into its use or significance while reflecting the annotator’s scholarly or personal perspective.

2.1 What is a Semantic Annotation

The discovery of information, whether physical or digital, relies on descriptive labels. In the digital environment, **metadata** plays a crucial role in organizing, identifying, and retrieving information. Metadata is often described as “data about data”, or, as defined by more precise definition:

“Metadata is structured, encoded data that describe the characteristics of information-bearing entities for purpose of identification, retrieval, evaluation, and administration of the described entities” (Durell 1985)

From a Semantic Web perspective, Tim Berners-Lee describes metadata as “*machine understandable information about web resources or other things*” (Berners-Lee 1997)

Metadata can be categorized into:

- **Structured Metadata:** Employing controlled vocabularies like Dublin Core to ensure consistency and machine-readability.
- **Unstructured Metadata:** Using free-text descriptions where semantics are less formalized.
- **Semantic Metadata:** Explicitly and formally defined metadata, often embedded within ontologies, enabling reasoning and computational understanding.

A critical dimension of metadata is **provenance**, which distinguishes between:

- **Authoritative Metadata:** Generated by trusted sources, such as cultural institutions or domain experts.
- **Non-authoritative Metadata:** User-generated, lacking institutional validation, and prone to inconsistency.

Annotations build upon the foundations of metadata by creating structured, meaningful connections between resources. In this context, **semantic annotation** refers to the process of attaching structured data (the annotation) to another data entity (the annotated object) and specifying the relationship between them. Semantic annotations can be represented formally as a tuple ($a_s - a_p - a_o - a_c$):

- a_s : the subject of the annotation (the annotated resource)
- a_o : the object of the annotations (the annotating data)
- a_p : the predicate (the annotation relation) that defines the type of relationship between a_s and a_o
- a_c : the context in which the annotation is made (e.g., provenance, date, or author).

For instance, when annotating a digitized manuscript, a_s might represent the digital representation of the manuscript, a_p could describe its relationship (“is authored by”), a_o might link to the author’s name, and a_c could specify when and by whom the annotation was created.

Annotations, therefore, reflect a particular perspective shaped by the circumstances of their creation, their intended conceptual purpose, and the annotator’s scholarly or personal viewpoint. This process of explicitly linking data in a dialogic structure situates the annotated object within a specific context, offering insights into its use and significance. From a semiotic point of view, it is underscored the importance of explanatory annotations in hermeneutics, emphasizing their critical role in interpretation and the pursuit of understanding (Elleström 2017).

Annotations can be described also as consisting of three layers: (1) the **annotatum**, which refers to the entity being annotated—the annotation target; (2) the **annotans**, which represents the content or commentary applied to the annotatum; and (3) the **annotator**, the agent who establishes the relationship between the annotans and the annotatum (Boot 2009). This concept is adapted to Target-Body relation theorized in WADM.

2.2 WADM’s Flexibility and Principles

The concepts of annotation relationships form the foundation of the **Open Annotation Ontology**⁴², a W3C standard introduced in 2013. It was developed by the **Web Annotation Working Group**,

⁴² <https://www.w3.org/ns/oa>

whose broader scope includes the development of server-side and client-side APIs and other essential components of the annotation architecture. The Open Annotation model specifies an **interoperable conceptual framework** for creating associations between related resources and annotations, using a methodology that conforms to the architecture of the *World Wide Web*. At the core of Open Annotation models is the **Body-Target structure** (see Figure 3), which defines the relationship between annotated objects and the annotations:

- **Target:** The annotated object (e.g., a text, image, or dataset).
- **Body:** The content of the annotation (e.g., a comment, interpretation, or related resource).

Figure 3 - Relations between the three major components of the Web Annotation standard(s).
(Source: <https://www.w3.org/TR/annotation-model/>)

For example, a researcher might annotate a historical painting (Target) with a description of its iconography (Body). The Open Annotation model encodes these relationships in RDF, ensuring that the annotation can be shared and reused across platforms.

Building on the Open Annotation model, **WADM** was developed to enhance practical implementation. While Open Annotation defines the conceptual framework for annotations, WADM formalizes it with standardized protocols and vocabularies, ensuring seamless integration across systems. Key components include:

- **Web Annotation Data Model:** Defines annotation as a linked resource with Body-Target relationships.
- **Web Annotation Vocabulary:** Specifies RDF classes, predicates, and terms to describe annotations consistently.
- **Web Annotation Protocol:** Establishes an HTTP API for creating, publishing, and retrieving annotations.

The **Open Annotation Ontology** serves as a conceptual framework, providing definitions for annotation relationships and their semantics. In contrast, WADM is a technical implementation model that ensures these conceptual structures are actionable in real-world applications.

For example:

- Open Annotation describes what annotations are and their relationships in principle (e.g., annotations have Bodies, Targets, and motivations).
- WADM specifies how annotations are serialized, exchanged, and queried using modern web technologies like **JSON-LD**.

The use of JSON-LD in WADM bridges the gap between Semantic Web technologies and web developers, enabling annotations to be represented as lightweight, human-readable JSON data while maintaining semantic richness. The following JSON-LD snippet illustrates an annotation linking a manuscript segment (Target) to its commentary (Body):

```
{
  "@context": "http://www.w3.org/ns/anno.jsonld",
  "id": "http://example.org/anno1",
  "type": "Annotation",
  "body": "http://example.org/comment1",
  "target": "http://example.org/resource1",
  "creator": "http://example.org/person1",
  "created": "2024-10-06T10:00:00Z"
}
```

The serialization of the Web Annotation model using JSON-LD provides a versatile and semantically rich representation of annotated data, aligning seamlessly with Linked Data principles. JSON-LD ensures easy integration into the broader Semantic Web ecosystem.

In WADM, the associated media type for JSON-LD serialization is defined as:

```
application/ld+json;profile=http://www.w3.org/ns/anno.jsonld
```

This establishes a standardized interpretation for processing JSON-LD data, ensuring that annotations remain both machine-readable and semantically interoperable, enabling their use across diverse platforms and applications.

The flexibility of WADM enables annotations to capture diverse relationships and data structures, including:

- **Annotations linking to external web resources** (e.g., references to external knowledge graphs).

- **Annotations embedding rich descriptive information** (e.g., linking a manuscript to its author with metadata).
- **Annotations defining hierarchical relationships**, connecting multiple resources.

For example, when a manuscript refers to a historical figure, WADM allows:

- If only identity information is available, the IRI of the person is directly linked.
- If detailed biographical data exists, the IRI is used as an `id` property, enabling integration with external databases and knowledge graphs.

This flexibility is particularly valuable in CH applications, where intricate connections between people, places, and artifacts need to be established and maintained.

WADM operates on foundational principles that define the relationships between resources within a rooted, directed graph. Annotations, being rooted, encapsulate a directed relationship between Bodies (content) and Targets (resources being annotated). These annotations may involve multiple Bodies and one or more Targets, enabling rich, multi-faceted relationships. The specifics of the Target or Body resource can extend beyond the resource's IRI alone, including specific segments, styles, states, or roles. WADM emphasizes that annotations are **web resources**, adhering to Linked Data principles. Common resource classes —such as `Dataset`, `Image`, `Video`, `Sound`, and `Text` —offer further clarity about the type of resource being annotated. Additionally, annotations may involve segments of external resources, identified using IRIs with fragment components, offering a means to precisely link and describe specific portions of resources, such as text segments or image regions.

2.2.1 Web Annotation Vocabulary

The **Web Annotation Vocabulary** defines the set of RDF classes, predicates and named entities used in WADM. It also specifies recommended terms from external metadata standards and provides the JSON-LD context and profile definitions necessary for using the Web Annotation JSON serialization in a Linked Data environment.

Key namespaces used in Web Annotation include:

- **oa**: The Web Annotation Data Model namespace, providing the core terms for defining annotations.
- **dc** and **dcterms**: Dublin Core namespaces, used for metadata such as creator and creation date.
- **schema**: Schema.org⁴³ terms, often used for broader compatibility.

⁴³ <https://schema.org/>

- **foaf**: Friend of a Friend (FOAF)⁴⁴, ideal for linking annotation to knowledge graphs or defining relationships between people.

These namespaces enable rich metadata integration through Dublin Core, offering comprehensive insights into the annotations' context. Additionally, the flexibility to integrate terms from multiple namespaces facilitates interoperability and allows for seamless connections to external resources. For instance, when annotating a manuscript that mentions an historical figure, the foaf namespace is useful for linking the annotation to an existing knowledge graph. Similarly, for multimedia annotations, such as associating an audio analysis with a patent document, the as (ActivityStreams⁴⁵) and dctypes (Dublin Core Types) namespaces can provide expressive capabilities.

2.2.2 Web Annotation Ontology

The Web Annotation Ontology builds on the Web Annotation Vocabulary, providing a semantic framework for defining relationships in annotations. It enables structured, machine-readable descriptions of annotations, ensuring interoperability across systems (see Figure 4). The following example, written in Turtle syntax, illustrates how the ontology links a Body (content) to a Target (resource):

```
<http://example.org/anno1> a oa:Annotation ;
  oa:hasBody <http://example.org/post1> ;
  oa:hasTarget <http://example.com/page1> ;
  oa:motivatedBy oa:commenting ;
  dcterms:creator <http://example.org/person1> ;
  dcterms:created "2015-11-18T12:00:00Z" .
```

In this example:

- **oa:Annotation** identifies the annotation as a resource.
- **oa:hasBody** specifies the content of the annotation.
- **oa:hasTarget** links to the annotated resource.
- **oa:motivatedBy** indicates the purpose of the annotation (e.g., commenting, tagging, classifying).
- **Dublin Core terms**, such as `dcterms:creator` and `dcterms:created`, provide provenance metadata (e.g., who created the annotation and when).

⁴⁴ <http://xmlns.com/foaf/spec/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.w3.org/ns/activitystreams>

By defining annotations in a structured manner, this approach ensures that annotations are semantically rich and interoperable, facilitating connections between digital resources and the broader web of knowledge. The Web Annotation Vocabulary and Ontology, with their associated namespaces and serialization formats, serve as foundational tools for creating meaningful and interoperable annotations. By enabling precise connections between Bodies and Targets, and supporting diverse metadata properties, these frameworks empower scholars to enrich digital objects with context and meaning. This approach not only aligns with Linked Data principles but also advances the goals of digital scholarship, ensuring that annotations contribute to a more interconnected and semantically rich scholarly environment.

Figure 4 - The class for Web Annotations. (Source: <https://www.w3.org/TR/annotation-vocab/>)

2.3 Beyond Web Annotation Data Model: Models and Practices

Previous sections have explored how images can be modeled semantically, enhancing their multi-layered descriptive capabilities. Additionally, IIIF has been examined as a solution for managing and delivering digital images with attached metadata using web standards. WADM has also been analyzed as a comprehensive framework for annotating and enriching digital objects.

Given the close relationship between IIIF and WADM, this section further investigates how these models intersect and complement each other, expanding the possibilities for semantic annotation and structured data representation in digital scholarship.

2.3.1 IIIF Annotations

Annotations are integral to the IIIF, serving both technical and descriptive functions. A primary technical application involves associating image resources with a digital canvas through the “painting” motivation. This process dictates how an image is rendered within a viewer, ensuring precise placement and display. While this technical detail might seem confusing at first glance, it is crucial to understand that annotations in IIIF serve not only as tools for commentary or tagging but also as mechanisms for rendering visual content onto a canvas.

To clarify this dual role, we turn to a recipe from the IIIF Cookbook that illustrates the painting motivation within a simple manifest example⁴⁶. This example demonstrates the structure of an annotation embedded in the manifest to “paint” an image onto the canvas:

```
"items": [
  {
    "id": "https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0001-mvm-
image/canvas/p1",
    "type": "Canvas",
    "height": 1800,
    "width": 1200,
    "items": [
      {
        "id": "https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0001-mvm-
image/page/p1/1",
        "type": "AnnotationPage",
        "items": [
          {
            "id": "https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0001-mvm-
image/annotation/p0001-image",
            "type": "Annotation",
            "motivation": "painting",
            "body": {
              "id":
"http://iiif.io/api/presentation/2.1/example/fixtures/resources/page1-
full.png",
              "type": "Image",
              "format": "image/png",
              "height": 1800,
              "width": 1200
            },
            "target": https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0001-mvm-
image/canvas/p1
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
]
```

⁴⁶ <https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0001-mvm-image/>

]

In this example:

- The motivation: "painting" indicates that the purpose of the annotation is to render an image on the canvas. Unlike other annotation motivations (e.g., commenting or tagging), the painting motivation is not defined by WADM but is specific to IIIF and critical to its architecture.
- The body property contains the actual image resource, detailing its format, dimensions, and location via its id.
- The target property identifies the canvas where the image will be displayed, providing a spatial context for rendering.

It is important to note that annotations with the painting motivation differ fundamentally from annotations meant for commentary or semantic enrichment. According to the IIIF documentation, annotations intended for commentary or external analysis must not use the painting motivation. Instead, they are often grouped within annotation pages separate from those used to render visual content on a canvas.

Moving forward, we examine a code snippet taken from the IIIF Cookbook that illustrates a tagging annotation⁴⁷:

```
    "annotations": [
      {
        "id": "https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0021-
tagging/page/p2/1",
        "type": "AnnotationPage",
        "items": [
          {
            "id": "https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0021-
tagging/annotation/p0002-tag",
            "type": "Annotation",
            "motivation": "tagging",
            "body": {
              "type": "TextualBody",
              "value": "Gänseliesel-Brunnen",
              "language": "de",
              "format": "text/plain"
            },
            "target": "https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0021-
tagging/canvas/p1#xywh=265,661,1260,1239"
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
```

⁴⁷ <https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0021-tagging/>

]

This example demonstrates a basic implementation of an Annotation with the `motivation` property set to `tagging`. This property indicates the purpose of the Annotation, in this case associating a keyword or tag—`Gänseliesel-Brunnen`—with a specific portion of the resource, identified by the `target` property. The tagged area on the canvas is defined using the `xywh` selector, which specifies the `x`, `y` coordinates and width and height of the rectangular region of interest. The inclusion of `motivation` is particularly important as it provides the “why” behind the annotation’s creation, complementing the “who” and “when” typically covered in other metadata.

While not shown in this example, IIF annotations can include a `behavior` property. When set to `hidden`, annotations, like tags, are not displayed by default in viewers, but users can toggle their visibility. This feature adds flexibility in managing annotations, especially in scenarios where certain metadata is relevant for backend processes but not for immediate user interaction.

Annotations in IIF extend beyond simple tagging, offering advanced features defined by the WADM. For instance, annotations can leverage segment selection through selectors like `FragmentSelector`, enabling precise targeting of specific regions within an image or segments of text. In some cases, the `target` property does not reference a content resource directly but instead points to a more abstract entity, such as a `SpecificResource` or a `Choice`. This approach is particularly valuable for scenarios requiring conditional logic or complex semantic relationships. The `body` property of an annotation further enhances its utility by supporting not only simple textual content but also complex formats, such as HTML or structured data, enabling richer semantic annotations.

To accommodate cases where the standard `FragmentSelector` is insufficient, the IIF community has defined additional `Selector` classes for use with `SpecificResource`. These extensions allow for more precise targeting, such as defining regions within complex layouts or addressing overlapping resources, thereby broadening the scope of IIF annotations. The documentation for these community contributions is available in the IIF specifications and associated repositories.

While tagging remains a common use case, IIF annotations also support a broader range of motivations defined in the WADM, such as `commenting`, `replying`, or `questioning`. The implementation and utility of these motivations often depend on viewer support and alignment with community priorities. Unique to IIF is the `painting` motivation, which signifies the rendering of content onto a `Canvas`, distinguishing it from annotations aimed at analysis or commentary. Less commonly used motivations, such as `questioning` or `replying`, could play a valuable role in collaborative or educational contexts. However, their successful adoption would require careful consideration to ensure compatibility with IIF viewers and workflows.

As already seen, the `seeAlso` property in IIIF plays a crucial role in linking external, machine-readable metadata to IIIF resources. This functionality is particularly valuable for aggregators and systems that process or index digital objects. By integrating structured metadata such as XML, JSON, or RDF through the `seeAlso` property, creators can enhance the discoverability of their resources while enabling advanced features like faceted search, which makes content easier to navigate and explore.

Unlike other properties in IIIF, such as `homepage`, which points to a human-readable webpage about the resource, or `rendering`, which links to alternate representations like PDFs or ePubs, `seeAlso` focuses on providing structured data specifically for machines. Another property, `accompanyingCanvas`, serves a complementary purpose by linking additional IIIF-compatible resources presented alongside the main object.

The `seeAlso` property is flexible and can be applied to any IIIF resource, including manifests and canvases. It requires certain key attributes to function effectively, including `id` (the URI of the external resource) and `type` (typically `Dataset`). Additional attributes, such as `label`, `format`, and `profile`, are strongly recommended to provide meaningful context about the linked metadata.

Here is an example⁴⁸ of a `seeAlso` property that links a MODS (Metadata Object Description Schema)⁴⁹ XML file to a manifest:

```
"seeAlso": [
  {
    "id": "https://fixtures.iiif.io/other/UCLA/ezukushi_mods.xml",
    "type": "Dataset",
    "label": {
      "en": [
        "MODS metadata"
      ]
    },
    "format": "text/xml",
    "profile": "http://www.loc.gov/mods/v3"
  }
]
```

In this example, the `id` points to the URI of the MODS XML file, and the `type` specifies that the resource is a dataset. The `label` provides a human-readable title for the linked metadata, and the `format` defines the file type as XML. The `profile` property indicates the schema used, in this case, the MODS specification.

⁴⁸ <https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0053-seeAlso/>

⁴⁹ <https://www.loc.gov/standards/mods/>

For aggregators, this setup allows efficient harvesting of metadata, enabling them to offer enhanced discovery tools to users. Viewers like Mirador also support the `seeAlso` property, displaying links to related metadata in their interface. For instance, users can access the linked metadata through the sidebar menu, where the “See also” section highlights additional resources connected to the manifest.

It is also possible to link external annotations targeting a Canvas to a Manifest. To ensure a resolvable link between annotations and the manifest containing their canvases, the `partOf` attribute can be employed within the source element of a `SpecificResource`. This approach is particularly useful for annotations stored in external Annotation Pages. Typically, annotations target a canvas or a canvas fragment, but without a resolvable canvas identifier, consuming viewers may encounter difficulties. By adding the `partOf` attribute, the manifest identifier is explicitly linked to the annotation's target, providing the viewer with access to the containing manifest.

In implementation, the `partOf` attribute resides within the source element, with its `id` pointing to the manifest's URI and its `type` set to “Manifest”. This establishes a clear and resolvable connection. Additionally, the `selector` attribute of the `SpecificResource` allows specifying a particular region within the canvas using a `FragmentSelector`. The value property in the selector adheres to the Media Fragment syntax (xywh format) to define coordinates for the targeted region.

In the provided example, an external Annotation Page references a specific region of a canvas, while also linking back to the manifest⁵⁰. We see the annotation page in this snippet:

```
"target": {
  "type": "SpecificResource",
  "source": {
    "id": "https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0306-linking-annotations-
to-manifests/canvas-1",
    "type": "Canvas",
    "partOf": [
      {
        "id": "https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0306-linking-
annotations-to-manifests/manifest.json",
        "type": "Manifest"
      }
    ]
  },
  "selector": {
    "type": "FragmentSelector",
    "conformsTo": "http://www.w3.org/TR/media-frags/",
    "value": "xywh=300,800,1200,1200"
  }
}
```

⁵⁰ <https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0306-linking-annotations-to-manifests/>

and the snippet relative to Manifest file:

```
"annotations": [  
  {  
    "id": "https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0306-linking-annotations-  
to-manifests/annotationpage.json",  
    "type": "AnnotationPage"  
  }  
]
```

This method eliminates ambiguity, ensuring that consuming viewers can trace annotations back to their original manifests and access the related context. However, for annotations embedded directly within a manifest, the `partOf` attribute is unnecessary, as the connection to the manifest is implicit. This approach is particularly beneficial for external Annotation Pages and facilitates better interoperability and discoverability in IIIF-compliant systems.

Besides the classical rectangular selection of an area, based on `xywh` coordinates, IIIF annotations support non-rectangular selections with the `SvgSelector`, allowing precise delineation of complex shapes. This feature, grounded in WADM, enables annotators to highlight irregularly shaped regions, such as intricate details in artwork or specific areas of a document. The `SvgSelector` employs **Scalable Vector Graphics (SVG)** markup to define these shapes, providing a flexible mechanism for targeting portions of a canvas that cannot be adequately described with simple rectangles.

The `SvgSelector` works by associating a `SpecificResource` with a canvas, where the selector property contains the SVG markup describing the shape. For instance, a polygonal path can be defined to highlight a statue on a fountain, ensuring that the annotation precisely matches the visual feature it is meant to address. Viewers render the SVG shapes over the canvas, but compatibility requires adhering to simplified SVG features such as named shapes, paths, and polygons. Overly complex SVGs with transformations or intricate styling may not render correctly across all IIIF-compliant viewers.

In the example below, an annotation highlights a statue using a polygon defined in SVG. The `SpecificResource` targets the relevant canvas, and the `SvgSelector` specifies the precise coordinates of the highlighted shape⁵¹:

```
"annotations": [  
  {  
    "id": "https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0261-non-rectangular-  
commenting/page/p2/1",
```

⁵¹ <https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0261-non-rectangular-commenting/>

```

    "type": "AnnotationPage",
    "items": [
      {
        "id": "https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0261-non-rectangular-
commenting/annotation/p0002-svg",
        "type": "Annotation",
        "motivation": "tagging",
        "body": {
          "type": "TextualBody",
          "value": "Gänseliesel-Brunnen",
          "language": "de",
          "format": "text/plain"
        },
        "target": {
          "type": "SpecificResource",
          "source": "https://iiif.io/api/cookbook/recipe/0261-non-
rectangular-commenting/canvas/p1",
          "selector": {
            "type": "SvgSelector",
            "value": "<svg xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg'><g><path
d='M270,1900 L1530,1900 L1530,1610 L1315,1300 L1200,986 L904,661
L600,986 L500,1300 L270,1630 L270,1900' /></g></svg>"
          }
        }
      }
    ]
  }
]

```

This capability broadens the range of use cases for IIIF annotations, from annotating irregular shapes in manuscripts and maps to cataloging detailed features in archaeological or artistic contexts.

How to store annotations

The IIIF ecosystem is fundamentally divided into server and client components, each playing a critical role in storing, delivering, and interacting with digital representations and annotations. Server components handle the storage and delivery of IIIF-compliant content, including images and annotations, while client software, such as viewers, enables users to interact with this content.

Image servers are responsible for delivering image resources compliant with the IIIF Image API. Popular open-source options⁵² include *Cantaloupe*⁵³, a Java-based solution known for its flexibility and ease of configuration, and *IIP Image Server*⁵⁴, a C++ implementation optimized for performance

⁵² <https://training.iiif.io/europeana/day-two/image-servers/>

⁵³ <https://cantaloupe-project.github.io/>

⁵⁴ <https://iipimage.sourceforge.io/>

and lightweight deployments. Institutions already using Digital Asset Management Systems (DAMS) or repositories can achieve IIIF compliance using middleware tools or “shims” such as *Flask-IIIF*⁵⁵, a Python library that extends Flask applications to serve IIIF-compliant content.

For institutions considering server options, it is advisable to choose tools that support the latest versions of the Image and Presentation APIs (both currently at version 3.0). A comprehensive list of IIIF-compliant image servers and related resources can be found in the Awesome IIIF GitHub repository⁵⁶.

Annotations can be stored in two primary ways: directly within the Manifest or in a separate annotation server.

Storing annotations directly in the Manifest integrates them tightly with the resource's metadata, simplifying workflows when annotations are static and closely tied to specific content. However, as annotations grow in number or complexity, this approach can bloat the Manifest and reduce performance. Annotation servers, by contrast, provide a scalable and flexible solution for storing and managing annotations. These servers are applications equipped with databases to handle API requests for creating, retrieving, updating, and deleting annotations. For example, Mirador sends a POST request containing the annotation data to an annotation server, which then stores the annotation and provides it with a unique identifier for persistent access.

Some of the most popular annotation servers include:

- **Elucidate**⁵⁷: A robust Java-based server using a Postgres database. Developed by *Digirati*, Elucidate offers high scalability and compliance with WADM.
- **SimpleAnnotationServer**⁵⁸: A Java-based server leveraging backends like Apache Jena triple store, Elastic Search, or Solr. Initially developed at the *National Library of Wales*, it supports complex annotation workflows.
- **Miiify**⁵⁹: A lightweight web annotation server designed specifically for IIIF applications. It separates annotations from manifests, simplifying manifests while providing persistent, uniquely identifiable access to annotations. Miiify adheres to WADM, organizing annotations into structured containers.

⁵⁵ <https://github.com/inveniosoftware/flask-iiif>

⁵⁶ <https://github.com/IIIF/awesome-iiif?tab=readme-ov-file#image-servers>

⁵⁷ <https://madoc.netlify.app/reference/modules/elucidate/>

⁵⁸ <https://github.com/glenrobson/SimpleAnnotationServer>

⁵⁹ <https://github.com/nationalarchives/miiify>

In addition to servers, several platforms integrate annotation functionality with collaborative tools and enhanced workflows:

- **Annotate**⁶⁰: A web-based application that stores annotations in GitHub repositories rather than a traditional database. This approach enables seamless integration with GitHub-hosted images and manifests, offering version control and transparency.
- **Recogito**⁶¹: A platform maintained by *Pelagios*, focused on collaborative document annotation. Designed for Digital Humanities applications, Recogito fosters linkages between historical resources and supports annotating texts, images, and maps.

Final consideration on IIIF annotations

Annotations are a core component of the IIIF framework, playing a pivotal role in how images, videos, and other multimedia are rendered, organized, and interacted with. Annotations serve as the mechanism for associating content with IIIF canvases, effectively “painting” images or videos onto a canvas, and enabling a broad range of functionalities, from commenting and tagging to linking external resources.

The stability of identifiers in IIIF is critical to maintaining the integrity of annotations. Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) and consistent URLs for manifests, canvas IDs, and image IDs ensure that annotations remain intact when content is moved across servers or viewed in different IIIF-compliant viewers. As in a IIIF training workshop⁶², changing or breaking these identifiers can lead to the loss of all annotations associated with a manifest. Therefore, institutions implementing IIIF are encouraged to adopt best practices such as configuring URL redirects if server changes occur. This consistency is essential for interoperability, particularly when annotations are shared, imported, or viewed in different systems.

Annotations in IIIF are defined by their “motivation”, which specifies the purpose of the annotation. Motivations derive either from the W3C Web Annotation Model or IIIF-specific extensions. Common motivations include commenting, tagging, and describing, though institutions must exercise caution when using fewer common motivations, as some IIIF viewers may only support specific types.

⁶⁰ <https://annotate.github.io/>

⁶¹ <https://recogito.pelagios.org/>

⁶² <https://training.iiif.io/iiif-online-workshop/day-four/>

The target of an annotation—the specific resource or part of a resource being annotated—can vary depending on the tools used. For instance, tools like Mirador allow for annotations to target specific regions of an image, enabling highly granular interactions with content.

When selecting tools for managing and viewing annotations, the choice of software and API versions is an important consideration. For instance, while Mirador 2 offers more advanced annotation functionalities, such as linking images and videos, Mirador 3 is designed to better interpret manifests created with the IIIF Presentation API version 3. The trade-off between feature richness and compatibility highlights the importance of aligning the toolset with the project's specific goals and the standards being adopted.

The IIIF Presentation API itself allows annotations to be embedded directly within manifests or linked externally via annotation pages. This flexibility supports a wide range of use cases, from embedding descriptive metadata to enabling interactive exploration of multimedia collections.

When discussing semantic annotation, the concept of Named Entity Recognition (NER) becomes highly relevant. NER is a natural language processing technique used to identify and classify entities—such as people, places, and dates—within a text. In the context of IIIF, NER can be employed to automatically generate annotations that enrich the semantic understanding of digital objects. For instance, an image of a historical document might be annotated with named entities extracted from its text, linking the identified entities to external knowledge bases like Wikidata⁶³ or the Getty Vocabularies⁶⁴. This approach not only enhances discoverability but also fosters connections between IIIF resources and the broader Linked Data ecosystem.

The annotation model in IIIF is a cornerstone of its interoperability-focused design. By adhering to standardized APIs and best practices for identifier management, institutions can ensure that their annotations remain stable, portable, and interoperable. Moreover, the collaborative development of IIIF—driven by libraries, archives, museums, and technologists—ensures that annotations remain a versatile tool for a wide range of cultural heritage applications. From rendering images on canvases to enabling advanced semantic connections through NER and Linked Data principles, annotations make IIIF a powerful framework for managing and exploring digital collections.

⁶³ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page

⁶⁴ <https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/>

2.3.2 Multi-Level Annotation Ontology

Building on the foundation provided by WADM, the **Multi-Level Annotation Ontology (MLAO)**⁶⁵ offers a robust framework for addressing semantic gaps in annotations, focusing on the annotation of images. Using technologies like RDF and JSON-LD, MLAO bridges the gap between human-readable annotations and machine-readable linked data, enabling interoperability across platforms.

As described in the recent paper that explores the multi-level approach to semantic annotation (Pedretti et al. 2024), MLAO extends WADM by incorporating key domain standards to represent the complexity of interpretative acts in digital and analog entities. In considering digital annotations as a general practice, WADM provides a foundational standard but lacks the semantic specificity required to represent the complexity of interpretative acts on both digital and analog entities. The proposed solution to this semantic deficit is introducing MLAO, which extends WADM by integrating domain-specific standards such as the Library Reference Model Ontology (LRMer)⁶⁶. Additionally, elements from the HiCO are incorporated to represent the context of hermeneutical activities performed by scholars while generating new information, such as an interpretation act. HiCO enables the inclusion of features like the criteria and types of cited sources. CIDOC-CRM and PROV-O standards are also utilized to define entity relationships and specify provenance.

Their work focuses on a compelling use case: the “*Vatican Palimpsests project*”⁶⁷, which employs IIF to create an interoperable framework for the collaborative annotation of digitized manuscripts. It introduces the following foundational concepts:

Aboutness: The annotation must reference the primary content (e.g., a text or other data) it comments on or explains. This reference can be explicit, such as a page number or citation, or implicit, inferred from the context in which the annotation appears.

Separateness: The annotation must be conceptually distinct from the main text or object it refers to. This distinction can be physical, such as a margin note or caption, or symbolic, as seen in hyperlinks. This also involves the nature of the medium that hosts the annotation. The support can be material, like a sticky note or a relational database, or immaterial, such as the mental content of the annotator.

Informativeness: The annotation must provide some form of informational content about its target. This content can range from detailed explanatory notes to a re-presentation of the

⁶⁵ <http://w3id.org/mlao> - <https://friendlynihilist.github.io/mlao/>.

⁶⁶ <https://www.iflstandards.info/lrm/lrmer.html>

⁶⁷ <https://spotlight.vatlib.it/palimpsests>

primary source in a different format, such as a transcription. However, informativeness does not necessarily require a structured annotation; it may include simple markers like exclamation points or underlining to emphasize or highlight elements of interest.

Perspectivism: The annotation should embody a specific interpretive choice made by the annotator, reflecting their perspective on the annotatum. This implies that the annotation highlights a particular aspect of the entity it refers to, emphasizing certain claims or observations over others.

These principles emphasize that annotations must clearly reference their targets, remain conceptually distinct, provide valuable insights, and reflect the annotator's interpretative choices. For example, in the context of annotating a digitized manuscript, the annotation might describe the manuscript's iconographic details while referencing the annotator's specific perspective. This separation between the annotated object and the annotation itself ensures a structured approach to scholarly practices, fostering a clearer understanding of the relationships between resources.

To apply the model to a real-world use case, they considered “*Vatican Palimpsests project*”, part of the broader one named “*Thematic Pathways on the Web*” developed by the Digital Vatican Library (DigiVatLib)⁶⁸ and started in 2016. This choice was made because an extensive annotation campaign had already been undertaken on the digitized collection, and also due to the complexity of the composite nature of the manuscripts themselves. Palimpsest manuscripts are texts in which the original writing has been erased and overwritten with new content. Existing annotations in this collection are categorized based on their type or motivation, including philological, paleographical, transcription, and commentary annotations. Additionally, information about the nature of the palimpsest is conveyed by specific tags, using unstructured labels such as *scriptio superior*, *scriptio inferior*, and *scriptio infima*. These labels are then used within a search engine for browsing and filtering the collection of annotations. While this tagging structure is useful for basic search and filtering functionalities, it does not fully leverage the potential of Linked Data principles. The proposed model aims to mitigate this issue of semantic deficit in digital annotations.

In the *Vatican Palimpsests* use case, MLO enables a nuanced representation of annotations tied to multi-layered cultural heritage objects. Annotations are linked to IIF Manifests through FRBRoo's `frbroo:F4_Manifestation` class, reflecting the digital representation of the analog object. This structure allows for annotations to refer not only to digital manifestations but also to conceptual levels such as FRBRoo's *Work* or *Expression*, as required by scholarly practice. For example, an annotation

⁶⁸ <https://spotlight.vatlib.it/>

targeting a specific area of a manuscript's image might reference a broader interpretative act involving the manuscript's historical or textual context.

Figure 5 - The formal model for the Multi-Level Annotation Ontology (MLAO). (Source: C.T. Pedretti et al., 2024, "What Do We Annotate When We Annotate? Towards a Multi-Level Approach to Semantic Annotations.")

Following the Web Annotation Ontology, an annotation is represented as an instance of the class `oa:Annotation`, with several associated properties and object classes:

- **The Target** (`oa:hasTarget`): The annotation is linked to a target (i.e., the annotatum) via the `oa:hasTarget` property. The target is represented by an instance of the `oa:SpecificResource` class, which identifies part of another resource, referenced using `oa:hasSource`. This source may represent a specific part of a resource, a styled version of the resource, or a combination of these. In the case of digital images or facsimiles using IIIF, the source is typically the **Canvas** that conveys the image. The property `oa:hasSelector` is then used to connect to an instance of `oa:FragmentSelector`, which specifies the coordinates of the segment or region of interest within the source resource.
- **The Body** (`oa:hasBody`): The annotation is linked to its body (i.e., the annotans) through the `oa:hasBody` property. The body is represented as an instance of the

oa:TextualBody class and contains the actual content of the annotation, such as unstructured textual data in the form of a comment, tag, or transcription.

- **The Motivation** (oa:hasMotivation): The annotation is connected to an instance of the oa:Motivation class via the oa:hasMotivation property. This property captures the intent of the annotator in creating the annotation, such as commenting, tagging, or transcribing.
- **The Author**: The author of the annotation is represented as an instance of the foaf:Person class, linked to the annotation through the dct:creator property, employing FOAF and Dublin Core Terms to specify the creator's identity.

A defining feature of MLA0 is the introduction of the concept of an **Anchor** represented by the class mlao:Anchor which describes the intentional object or referent of the annotation that can differ from the target itself. It is connected to the oa:Annotation class through the property mlao:hasAnchor. This duality allows MLA0 to connect annotations not only to the immediate resource being annotated (e.g., an IIF Manifest) but also to the underlying real-world referent described using the FRBRoo framework. This Anchor instance is connected via the mlao:hasConceptualLevel property to an instance of one of the FRBRoo types—frbroo:F1_Work, frbroo:F2_Expression, frbroo:F4_Manifestation, or frbroo:F5_Item—to describe its conceptual level within the FRBR framework. Furthermore, the Anchor is linked to its real-world counterpart through the mlao:isAnchoredTo property, which references an instance of the work it refers to, represented as an entity identified by a URI. By associating the annotation with both a referent in the “real world” (via the URI) and a specific area in a piece of media that captured it (e.g., the target), this approach minimizes the semantic deficit between the annotation and the annotated object. This dual linkage enhances the computer’s ability to process and generalize the connections, enabling more effective utilization of the relationships in computational and semantic environments.

MLA0 also supports modeling annotations as the outcomes of interpretation acts, a concept central to HiCO. These acts are represented by the hico:InterpretationAct class, which links annotations to the motivations, criteria, and sources underlying their creation. For example, a philological interpretation of a palimpsest's scriptio infima could be connected to its digital representation via the FRBRoo *Manifestation* level, while also capturing the interpretative methodology used, such as diplomatic transcription.

The practical utility of MLA0 was demonstrated through its integration into a prototype annotation plugin for the Mirador viewer. This tool facilitates the creation of multi-level semantic annotations in a collaborative environment, ensuring that annotations remain interoperable and semantically rich. From a user interface perspective, five autocomplete dropdowns were integrated to streamline the

annotation process. These dropdowns allow users to select options from predefined taxonomies or create new entries dynamically. They manage various aspects of annotations, including the **Conceptual Level**, **Anchor**, **Referenced Entity**, **Interpretation Criterion**, and **Editor** (see Figure 6).

Figure 6 - A screenshot of the Mirador Multi-Level Annotation plugin prototype. (Source: C.T. Pedretti et al., 2024, "What Do We Annotate When We Annotate? Towards a Multi-Level Approach to Semantic Annotations.")

The custom dropdowns dynamically inject extended metadata into the JSON-LD output generated by Mirador, ensuring seamless integration of the enhanced data model into the existing infrastructure without compromising the user experience.

The implementation utilized React for the front-end development and the JSON-LD processor library⁶⁹ to convert JSON-LD into RDF serializations. The dropdowns were designed to support CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations on a *Blazegraph*⁷⁰ triplestore using SPARQL. They were also populated with data retrieved via SPARQL queries, ensuring both the persistent storage of annotations in a dedicated triple store and full interoperability with other Semantic Web technologies.

2.3.3 LOUD and Linked Art

Interlinking CH data is essential for publishing heritage collections on the web, particularly through LOD technologies, which enhance machine readability and semantic richness. Given the complexity and interconnectivity of CH data, integrating controlled vocabularies and ontologies with web standards ensures interoperability across platforms

⁶⁹ <https://github.com/digitalbazaar/jsonld.js>

⁷⁰ <https://github.com/blazegraph/database>

Despite advancements in CH data interlinking, challenges persist, particularly in balancing completeness and precision while maintaining accessibility for diverse audiences. The **Linked Open Usable Data (LOUD) principles**⁷¹, along with specifications such as the **IIIF Presentation API 3.0** and **Linked Art**⁷², offer practical solutions by prioritizing **usability** (Raemy et al., 2023). By emphasizing the needs of software developers and data scientists, LOUD facilitates the design of visualization tools and data aggregation strategies, improving the overall user experience (Sanderson, 2019). Together, these technologies and methodologies illustrate how structured, interoperable, and usable data can redefine the way we engage with CH collections.

Attaching a semantic layer to data, in line with the **DIKW (Data-Information-Knowledge-Wisdom) pyramid**⁷³, aims to transform data into actionable knowledge. The seamless exchange of this semantic information between distinct systems is what constitutes semantic interoperability. This interoperability is central to the open vision of the Web, ensuring that academic and cultural heritage data are freely accessible and reusable by a broad spectrum of users. So, the emphasis is shifting from merely publishing data to the actual usability and practical consumption. Crucially, usability is determined by the needs of the audience consuming the data, rather than solely by the preferences of the publishers. Developers and designers act as key intermediaries between data and researchers, making their participation fundamental to the Semantic Web's practical applications.

API, often referred to as the developer's user interface, play a crucial role in this dynamic:

“When it comes to APIs, developers are your users. The same principles of user-centred-design apply to the development and publication of APIs (simplicity, obviousness, fit-for-purpose etc.).” (API Guide)

However, within the LOD environment, the usability of APIs presents unique challenges. APIs for LOD are often structured around ontologies, with RDF and SPARQL serving as the open standards for querying and retrieving data. While this approach addresses the needs of data publishers, it does not always align with the expectations of developers, who require APIs that are intuitive, user-friendly, and easy to implement. As a result, the expressivity of open standards—particularly the intricate extensions of CIDOC-CRM—can sometimes compromise usability. This highlights the need to prioritize user-centered API design, balancing semantic richness with practical accessibility to ensure broader adoption and engagement in digital humanities and cultural heritage projects.

⁷¹ <https://linked.art/loud/>

⁷² <https://linked.art/>

⁷³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/DIKW_pyramid

Robert Sanderson (2019) emphasized that for data to be truly usable, it must adhere to five core features, collectively known as the LOUD design principles. These principles, which parallel Tim Berners-Lee's *Five Star Open Data Deployment Scheme*⁷⁴, aim to bridge the gap between data publishers' requirements and the practical needs of developers and end-users. They are as follows:

A. The right **A**bstraction for the audience

Developers do not need the same level of access to data as ontologists, in the same way that a driver does not need the same level of access to the inner workings of their car as a mechanic. Use cases and requirements should drive the interoperability layer between systems, not ontological purity.

B. Few **B**arriers to entry

It should be easy to get started with the data and build something. If it takes a long time to understand the model, ontology, sparql query syntax and so forth, then developers will look for easier targets. Conversely, if it is easy to start and incrementally improve, then more people will use the data.

C. **C**omprehensible by introspection

The data should be understandable to a large degree simply by looking at it, rather than requiring the developer to read the ontology and vocabularies. Using JSON-LD lets us to talk to the developer in their language, which they already understand.

D. **D**ocumentation with working examples

You can never intuit all the rules for the data. Documentation clarifies the patterns that the developer can expect to encounter, such that they can implement robustly. Example use cases allow contextualization for when the pattern will be encountered, and working examples let you drop the data into the system to see if it implements that pattern correctly.

E. Few **E**xceptions, instead many consistent patterns

Every exception that you have in an API (and hence ontology) is another rule that the developer needs to learn to use the system. Every exception is jarring and requires additional code to manage. While not everything is homogenous, a set of patterns that manage exceptions well is better than many custom fields.

⁷⁴ <https://5stardata.info>

These principles directly tackle the challenges of usability in Linked Open Data, promoting a shift from theoretical completeness to practical accessibility. By aligning with these design goals, the LOUD principles aim to bridge the gap between complex semantic models and the operational needs of developers, designers, and researchers. Overall, the main intention of LOUD is to provide **straightforward access to data**, primarily for software developers. This necessitates establishing a balance that addresses the dual demands of data completeness and accuracy, grounded in the ontological construct, and the **pragmatic concerns of scalability and ease of use**. By prioritizing usability alongside openness, LOUD ensures that Linked Data can meet the diverse needs of both technical and non-technical audiences, driving its adoption and real-world application.

Linked Art

The Linked Art project exemplifies the application of LOUD principles in CH data modeling. As stated by two of its founders, Julien A. Raemy and Robert Sanderson (2023, 9):

“Linked Art is a community-driven initiative collaborating to define a metadata application profile, the model, to describe cultural heritage, and the technical means, a RESTful API, for conveniently interacting with it.”

The project is based on a communitarian spirit, and it is a CIDOC (ICOM) Working Group that collaborates to define a metadata application profile for describing CH, which specifies APIs that enable access to data.

Linked Art employs the JSON-LD serialization format for RDF, integrating Getty vocabularies⁷⁵ such as the **Arts & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT)**, the **Thesaurus of Geographic Names (TGN)**, and the **Union List of Artist Names (ULAN)**. It also leverages commonly used RDF ontologies like **RDF Schema (RDFS)**⁷⁶ and **Dublin Core** to disambiguate closely related property names used by CIDOC-CRM (Newbury 2018).

The project is based on the LOUD model, which is collaboratively designed to work across cultural heritage organizations and its design focus primarily on **usability and ease of implementation, more than completeness**. In fact, the aim is to *“solve the 90% of use cases, with 10% of the effort”*⁷⁷.

At its core, Linked Art adopts an **event-centric model** instead of the traditional object-centric approach. This event-based structure aligns with CIDOC-CRM principles and enables institutions to

⁷⁵ <https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/>

⁷⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/>

⁷⁷ https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/sanderson_newbury_linkedartgetty.pdf

model activities and relationships around cultural heritage objects. For instance, it facilitates answering key provenance questions—what, when, where, who, and how—while also supporting complex modeling of temporal data (see Figure 7).

Figure 7 - *Linked Art from 50,000 feet*. (Source: Sanderson, R., 2020, "The Importance of being LOUD." LODLAM 2020 Los Angeles, CA. <https://www.slideshare.net/azaro42/the-importance-of-being-loud>)

This approach enables the discovery of relationships, detailed tracking of changes, and robust historical analysis. To further understand its applicability, let us delve into the conceptual model underpinning Linked Art. Documented incrementally and influenced heavily by common use cases compiled transparently through GitHub issues, the model emphasizes practical solutions for structuring cultural heritage data (Raemy and Sanderson 2023).

The high-level conceptual model of Linked Art leverages CIDOC-CRM classes and addresses key provenance questions—"what", "where", "who", "how", and "when"—paralleling the *W7 model* developed by Ram and Liu (2019) for capturing provenance semantics. The model is structured into interconnected components, balancing shared baseline patterns with unique structures tailored to specific needs. These patterns, derived from practical applications with museum datasets, offer a robust foundation for organizing cultural heritage information.

Linked Art's model, like other LOD frameworks, defines core properties that every resource must include to ensure compatibility and usability as linked data⁷⁸. These include:

- `@context`: References the mapping context that determines how JSON is interpreted as LOD. It is not a property of the entity itself but of the document.
- `id`: Captures the URI uniquely identifying the resource. It must be an HTTP URI and is required for each resource.
- `type`: Corresponds to `rdf:type` in RDF, indicating the class of the resource. Each resource must have one class to enable alignment with class-based object-oriented implementations.
- `_label`: Provides a human-readable string describing the resource, useful for developers or consumers inspecting the data. While multilingual labels are not included here, implementations can support multiple languages when required.

CIDOC-CRM serves as a framework that requires extension to meet specific application needs. Linked Art achieves this by leveraging additional vocabularies and ontologies. For instance, the `classified_as` property extends the description of objects with controlled vocabulary terms. This differs from the `type` property, which is reserved for CIDOC-CRM classes and select extensions.

Below is a JSON-LD snippet that demonstrates how to classify a resource as a painting (using Getty AAT terms):

```
{
  "@context": "https://linked.art/ns/v1/linked-art.json",
  "id": "https://linked.art/example/object/20",
  "type": "HumanMadeObject",
  "_label": "Simple Example Painting",
  "classified_as": [
    {
      "id": "http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300033618",
      "type": "Type",
      "_label": "Painting"
    },
    {
      "id": "http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300133025",
      "type": "Type",
      "_label": "Work of Art"
    }
  ]
}
```

The Linked Art conceptual model includes patterns for describing objects, people, organizations, places, provenance, collections, exhibitions, and digital integration (e.g., leveraging IIIF). These

⁷⁸ <https://linked.art/model/base/>

patterns, vetted by the community, play a crucial role in organizing data related to artworks, artists, historical contexts, and metadata, creating an interconnected web of CH information.

The LOUD Ecosystem

When combined, the systems described—IIF, the LOUD design system, and Linked Art—create the **LOUD Ecosystem**, a framework that emphasizes seamless interoperability between independently developed systems (see Figure 8).

Figure 8 - LOUD Ecosystem. (Source: Raemy, J.A., Sanderson, R., 2023, “Analysis of the Usability of Automatically Enriched Cultural Heritage Data.”)

By adhering to the LOUD principles, these systems exemplify how collaborative design and shared standards can create a connected digital environment that supports accessibility, usability, and scalability in the CH sector.

2.3.4 ProDEM Case Study

The ProDem project⁷⁹ (full title: “*ProDem: I manoscritti epigrafici del senatore Filippo Buonarroti alla Marucelliana. Un progetto di digitalizzazione*”) is an initiative funded by the *Italian Ministry of University and Research*. It is coordinated by Professor Giovanni A. Cecconi (University of Florence, Department of Literature and Philosophy) in collaboration with Professor Silvia Orlandi (University of Rome “La Sapienza,” Department of Ancient Sciences) and Professor Antonio E. Felle (University of Bari, Department of Humanities Research and Innovation). The project aims to digitize and enhance access to the epigraphic manuscripts of Filippo Buonarroti (1661–1733), which are primarily

⁷⁹<https://marucelliana.cultura.gov.it/2024/10/07/10-ottobre-progetto-prodem-i-manoscritti-epigrafici-del-senatore-filippo-buonarroti-alla-marucelliana-un-progetto-di-digitalizzazione/>

housed in the *Biblioteca Marucelliana* in Florence. The digital platform developed as part of this initiative is accompanied by research initiatives, seminars, and publications.

As part of my internship work on this project, I focused on researching IIIF solutions to determine the most suitable image viewer and annotation storage method. These options included saving annotations in local storage, embedding them directly in the IIIF Manifest, or utilizing annotation servers.

The ProDEM project centered on integrating IIIF annotations into Muruca⁸⁰, an open-source framework for archiving, organizing, managing, publishing, and disseminating digital objects and collections developed by Net7⁸¹. Unlike a traditional CMS, Muruca is composed of modular components, leveraging WordPress, Fedora, and Solr for backend infrastructure, and using a dedicated AngularJS-based frontend connected via open APIs.

Within this framework, the ProDEM data model structured content from the manuscript level down to individual pages, treating each image as a digital resource. Annotations were linked to these images, with a further requirement to associate them with other entities, such as epigraphic objects.

The IIIF integration was structured in three key phases:

1. IIIF Server Integration

- Installed Cantaloupe, an IIIF-compliant image server, on the project's infrastructure.
- Developed a custom WordPress plugin to manage the migration of images to the IIIF server.

2. IIIF Manifest Generation

- Dynamically generated IIIF Manifests (manifest.json files) to reflect the logical structure of the data model.
- Ensured seamless navigation between images while adhering to IIIF Presentation API specifications.
- Integration of Mirador for Annotation Management

3. Implemented Mirador, as widely used IIIF-compliant viewer, to facilitate image annotation.

- Enabled synchronization of annotations with the WordPress database, allowing users to edit annotations within a familiar interface.
- Developed functionality to associate annotations with other entities in the database.

⁸⁰ <https://www.muruca.org/>

⁸¹ <https://www.netseven.it/>

- Allowed exporting of annotations back into the IIIF Manifest to ensure compatibility with the IIIF ecosystem.

The annotation workflow involved two main steps:

1. Writing the annotation: Users created annotations directly in Mirador. These annotations were sent to the annotation server via API and stored in the designated system using standardized specifications like the WADM.
2. Reading and displaying the annotation: Once recorded, annotations were immediately retrieved by Mirador through the same API, ensuring they were visible to users in real time.

Figure 9 - ProDEM interface.

Managing annotations in the WordPress backend provided a more integrated editing experience, aligning with the data model. However, a significant challenge was the need to operate within two separate environments for annotation editing, which required careful synchronization.

The ProDEM project provided a valuable opportunity to explore the technical and conceptual aspects of IIIF-based annotation management in a cultural heritage context. By leveraging Mirador and annotation servers, a flexible, standards-compliant solution was developed, ensuring:

- Interoperability within the broader IIIF ecosystem
- Scalability for future annotation expansions
- Sustainability for long-term CH data management

This experience highlighted the potential and limitations of IIIF annotations, particularly in relation to structured epigraphic metadata and linked cultural heritage data. The project demonstrated how

IIIF can enhance accessibility, usability, and scholarly engagement with digitized manuscripts and historical records.

2.3.5 LUX Case Study

The “*LUX: Yale Collections Discovery*” project⁸², developed by *Yale University*, represents a comprehensive implementation of the LOUD ecosystem, combining Linked Art and IIIF to create a seamless, user-friendly platform for discovering and researching Yale’s vast cultural heritage collections. The platform integrates collections from the *Yale Center for British Art (YCBA)*, the *Yale University Art Gallery (YUAG)*, the *Yale Peabody Museum (YPM)*, and the *Yale University Library (YUL)*. Its primary aim is to foster engagement, encourage teaching and learning, and spark curiosity while addressing the dual responsibility of preserving and making cultural heritage objects accessible.

Given the diverse domains and standards across Yale’s institutions, integrating systems and ensuring interoperability posed significant challenges. Existing standards and systems had to be unified without disrupting institutional workflows, and the platform needed to cater to a broad audience, from scholars and domain experts to students and casual users. The LUX platform achieves this by adhering to the principles of usability and interoperability central to the LOUD design system.

The solution encompasses several interconnected components, including:

- **Data Harvesting and Transformation:** Internal records from different institutions are transformed into Linked Art JSON format, ensuring consistency.
- **Data Pipeline and Reconciliation:** A data transformation and reconciliation process harmonizes disparate data formats, matching records and enriching them with external sources like Wikidata.
- **Back-End Database:** A robust data storage layer supports the platform’s operations.
- **Middle Tier and APIs:** Standards-based APIs ensure modularity and replaceability of components.
- **Front-End Interface:** The user interface fosters serendipitous discovery through a well-organized knowledge graph.

This modular design ensures that individual components can be replaced or upgraded independently, adhering to best practices for scalability and flexibility.

⁸² <https://lux.collections.yale.edu/>

Figure 10 - LUX Data Pipeline and Architecture. (Source: Raemy, J.A., Sanderson, R., 2023, . Analysis of the Usability of Automatically Enriched Cultural Heritage Data.)

LUX utilizes Linked Art as the foundation for its knowledge graph. As seen earlier, Linked Art adopts an event-centric model, expanding the CIDOC-CRM ontology to emphasize activities and relationships over isolated data points. This activity-centric approach is particularly effective for organizing and relating information from diverse sources, as it highlights the interactions between entities (artworks, people, places) over time.

Key top-level classes modeled in the knowledge graph include:

- **Objects:** HumanMadeObject, Digital Object
- **Work:** Linguistic and Visual Work
- **People & Organizations**
- **Concepts:** Types, Terminologies (e.g., AAT terms)
- **Places**
- **Events:** Provenance Events, Exhibitions

By relying on Getty Vocabularies like the Art and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT), LUX ensures semantic interoperability, enabling consistent descriptions of shared concepts (e.g., “painting” as a shared definition across institutions).

The user interface of LUX reflects the event-centric model, organizing information around key relationships like equivalents, which link objects with their related records. For instance, reconciled Wikidata records allow for meaningful connections between works in the YCBA collection and related items across Yale's other institutions. This unified interface supports both granular exploration and broad, cross-collection discovery.

Yale's implementation demonstrates the potential of the LOUD ecosystem to address longstanding challenges in the cultural heritage sector. Many institutions struggle to adopt open APIs due to resource constraints, lack of awareness, or implementation complexity. However, the integration of IIF and Linked Art within LUX provides a pathway to robust data pipelines, reconciliation, and enrichment, showcasing how open standards can significantly enhance data accessibility and interoperability.

The success of LUX underscores the value of combining the LOUD design principles with domain-specific specifications. It serves as a model for how cultural heritage institutions can embrace open data standards to create scalable, interoperable platforms that promote research, education, and public engagement.

3. LISA: Linked Interpretative Semantic Annotation Model

As previously discussed in this thesis, annotations play a vital role in scholarly work by enabling the creation of new knowledge. Although existing standards such as WADM and delivery platforms like IIIF provide a strong foundation for associating structured annotations with images, they often lack the semantic depth demanded by advanced research scenarios. This gap, highlighted by scholars such as Bradley (2012), underscores the need for **domain-specific extensions** that accommodate multiple interpretative levels, handle nuanced provenance requirements, and support versioning across collaborative environments. Furthermore, the use of JSON-LD serialization can enhance **usability standards**, making it easier to share and reuse these annotations across different platforms.

According to WADM, an annotation consists primarily of two elements:

- A **body** (*annotans*) – usually textual, though it may also be any type of resource.
- A **target** (*annotatum*) – in the IIIF context, typically a selector composed of coordinates defining a specific area of the Canvas within a Manifest.

WADM also supports supplementary information—such as **creation time**, **authorship**, and **motivation**—but does not inherently address the **richer semantic requirements** of scholarly research. Consequently, while WADM’s core structure (an annotation with `oa:hasBody`, `oa:hasTarget`, and `oa:motivatedBy`) is well-suited for straightforward use cases, it lacks explicit mechanisms for:

- **Multiple interpretative layers**, such as distinguishing between pre-iconographic and iconological insights.
- **Complex provenance chains** that record the evolution of interpretations and the agents responsible for them.
- **Anchoring mechanisms** that differentiate between digital and analog entities, and that enable referencing distinct segments of a single resource.

To address these requirements, this chapter introduces the **Linked Interpretative Semantic Annotation (LISA) Model**⁸³. Built on WADM, LISA extends its capabilities by integrating:

- **MLAO** for anchoring annotations
- **ICON** for iconographical recognition levels based on Panofsky’s interpretative framework
- **HiCO** for modeling scholarly interpretation acts
- **PROV-O** for capturing provenance, activities, and agents associated with annotations

⁸³ <https://github.com/sterenz/LISA>

By creating this anchor, LISA distinguishes between the physical artifact (e.g., a painting) and its digital representation, thus allowing for fine-grained or multi-layered analysis within digital tools.

Building on Erwin Panofsky’s framework, LISA uses the ICON ontology to formalize three interpretative levels:

- `icon:Pre-iconographicalRecognition` – Identifying basic shapes, forms, or objects (e.g., “a man”, “a tree”).
- `icon:IconographicalRecognition` – Identifying specific artistic motifs, symbols, or figures (e.g., “the figure is St. John”).
- `icon:IconologicalRecognition` – Providing broader cultural or ideological interpretations (e.g., “this painting symbolizes the Fall of Man”).

All three subclasses derive from the superclass `icon:Recognition` and are associated with the anchor (via `mlao:hasConceptualLevel`). Higher-level interpretations can refer back to earlier recognitions using properties like `icon:refersToArtisticMotif`, `icon:hasImage`, or `icon:hasArtisticMotif`, thus constructing a chain of meaning (see Figure 12). For instance, if at the pre-iconographic level a figure is recognized as a “woman”, the iconographical level may assert she is “Venus”, and the iconological level might contextualize her within a broader mythological or cultural narrative.

Figure 12 - An overview on LISA's recognition module.

In this way, `icon:Pre-iconographicalRecognition` may serve as the “conceptual entity” that `icon:IconographicalRecognition` or `icon:IconologicalRecognition` annotations build upon—essentially **creating annotations about annotations**.

3.2 Modeling Versioning and Provenance

Beyond anchoring and multi-level recognition, **provenance** and **versioning** are fundamental concerns in scholarly work. Annotations often evolve over time, with **multiple agents** contributing, revising, or even disputing earlier interpretations.

LISA integrates the Historical Context Ontology (HiCO) to model the interpretive process itself (see Figure 13). Specifically, each annotation can be linked to a `hico:InterpretationAct` via `prov:wasGeneratedBy`, indicating the scholarly activity or process that gave rise to the claim. The `hico:InterpretationAct` class also enables:

- **Interpretation type** (via `hico:hasInterpretationType`), defining the nature of the interpretation (e.g., authorship attribution, iconographic identification).
- **Interpretation criterion** (via `hico:hasInterpretationCriterion`), specifying the sources or methodologies (e.g., bibliographic references, scholarly consensus).
- **Citation links** (via properties like `cito:disagreesWith`), allowing scholars to express disagreements with other interpretations.

Figure 13 - An overview on LISA's interpretation module.

This last point is particularly important in digital humanities, where **subjective interpretations** are common. For example, if one scholar identifies a “woman” as “Venus”, another may disagree and propose “Diana” based on alternative evidence. Both claims can coexist, with each new interpretation recorded as a discrete `hico:InterpretationAct`, thereby preserving the discourse within the annotation set.

Modeling **who** made an annotation, **when**, and **why** is fundamental for establishing scholarly credibility and tracing interpretive evolutions. To support these requirements, LISA adopts both PROV-O and PRO.

PROV-O provides a framework to describe the creation of any digital entity (e.g., an annotation) and to link that entity to the activity and agents involved in its production.

Key Properties used in LISA are:

- `prov:wasGeneratedBy` records how a `hico:InterpretationAct` (and therefore the annotation itself) originated, capturing the specific scholarly activity or process that gave rise to a claim.
- `prov:wasAttributedTo` specifies the person or institution responsible for generating or endorsing the annotation.

In LISA, these PROV-O properties are used to document the life cycle of an annotation, providing transparency on who introduced or revised an interpretation, when that happened, and what motivated the change. This level of detail is particularly vital in art history, where attributions and identifications may shift over time due to new evidence or reexamination (see Figure 14).

Figure 14 – An overview on LISA's versioning module.

PRO, on the other hand, is an OWL 2 DL ontology designed to **characterize the roles of agents** (individuals, organizations, or computational agents) within a publication process. It not only distinguishes different roles (e.g., editor, publisher, reviewer) but also frames these roles within specific time intervals.

Key Classes and Properties integrated in LISA are:

- `pro:Role` indicates the function or responsibility (e.g., “Publisher”).
- `pro:RoleInTime` defines the temporal context during which an agent holds a specific role.
- `pro:holdsRoleInTime` links a `foaf:Agent` to its `pro:RoleInTime`, recording who does what, and when.

While PROV-O and PRO provide the foundational vocabulary for attributing creation events, agent responsibilities, and temporal information, LISA introduces additional domain-specific constructs to handle annotation versioning and editorial states:

- `lisa:PublishingStage`: captures the status of an annotation at any point in time. Designed for collaborative environments, annotations (or the interpretations they contain) can move through editorial workflows, from drafts to published versions, and potentially even to deprecated status if newer research supersedes earlier claims. Accordingly, LISA defines three key subclasses:
 - `lisa:Draft` – an annotation that is not yet peer-reviewed or officially endorsed.
 - `lisa:Published` – an annotation that has passed a review process and is widely accepted within the scholarly community or project context.
 - `lisa:Deprecated` – an annotation that has been superseded by new evidence or significantly revised interpretations.
- `lisa:hasStage`: links an annotation (`oa:Annotation`) to its current publishing stage (`lisa:PublishingStage`). Combined with PRO roles, it enables a clear distinction between who can authorize or change the annotation’s status. For instance, while anyone might create a Draft annotation, only an agent holding a publisher role (via `pro:holdsRoleInTime`) can transition it to Published.

By defining `lisa:hasStage`, LISA accommodates dynamic scholarly discourse—where new data, emerging consensus, or alternative perspectives may lead to the replacement of existing annotations. For example, an iconographical interpretation once considered definitive (e.g., identifying a figure as “Venus”) can be deprecated if new research suggests the figure is “Diana”. Through the PRO-based role system, LISA records who makes that change and when, enabling a fully traceable editorial process.

In sum, PRO and PROV-O fill the crucial gap of provenance and role-based workflow in LISA, allowing it to function as an end-to-end solution for semantic image annotation: from the inception of a claim (`InterpretationAct`) to its versioning and final editorial state (`PublishingStage`).

3.3 Competency Questions

In order to evaluate the extended model and verify that it supports the intended annotation features, the following competency questions are posed. These questions help determine whether LISA successfully captures the required information for scholarly art-historical research:

1. **Which recognition level is associated with a specific annotation?**

- Ensures that the model can distinguish between pre-iconographical, iconographical, and iconological interpretations at the annotation level.
2. **How many annotations on a particular Canvas express conflicting interpretations (e.g., one scholar disagrees with another)?**
 - Demonstrates the model’s ability to record and track multiple, possibly divergent `hico:InterpretationAct` instances referring to the same target.
 3. **How many annotations reference the same IIF resource but contain different anchors or conceptual levels?**
 - Shows whether LISA can handle multiple annotated regions or interpretative levels within a single digital object.
 4. **Which annotations at a given level of recognition were created by a specific author (`foaf:Person`)?**
 - Tests the model’s provenance-tracking features and the categorization of recognition levels.
 5. **Which annotations have transitioned from “Draft” to “Published” status, and who authorized that change?**
 - Validates the model’s capacity for role-based versioning and workflow management using `lisa:PublishingStage` and the Publishing Roles Ontology.

By addressing these competency questions, LISA’s effectiveness and completeness in capturing semantic annotations, provenance information, interpretive acts, and editorial states can be thoroughly assessed.

3.4 Data Model

Because LISA is built atop WADM, it remains fully compatible with IIF. Scholars using an IIF-compliant viewer (such as *Mirador*) can seamlessly select regions of an artwork and attach LISA annotations to them, enriched with anchors, interpretation acts, recognition levels, and provenance details. This compatibility allows for:

- Precise identification of a painting’s segment (via IIF coordinates).
- Rich semantic descriptions linking to external ontologies.
- Collaborative lifecycle tracking of annotations, from initial drafts to published states, managed by role-based controls.

To demonstrate LISA’s **practical value**, the next chapter explores how these annotation structures can be **implemented** within *Mirador*, a widely used IIF-based viewing platform. Key steps include:

- Customizing UI to display multi-level interpretative data, allowing users to view or hide specific recognition layers (pre-iconographical, iconographical, iconological).
- Embedding provenance and versioning widgets to trace the author, status, and source of each interpretative act.
- Managing collaborative roles so that only certain users can update or publish annotations, while others may contribute drafts or references.

These steps will illustrate LISA's capacity not only to theoretically model complex annotations but also to operationalize them in a standard scholarly workflow.

4. Semiotic and Hermeneutic of Annotations

Visualization has become a common method for communicating complex data, and with modern technologies, there is an increasing need to incorporate interactivity and to reflect the subjectivity inherent in CH data. In its early phases, digital data visualization often fell into two extremes: on one hand, overly complex infographics featuring unreadable 3D designs or futuristic translucent interfaces; on the other, overly simplistic approaches that falsely suggested all complexities could be reduced to a handful of pictograms and large numbers, thereby oversimplifying the narrative.

As Giorgia Lupi notes in her article⁸⁴, **complexity** is something we must embrace, especially when dealing with CH data. While the primary purpose of data visualization is to facilitate knowledge interpretation, entirely avoiding complexity when describing intricate contexts is often impractical. In the DH, data is deeply **interconnected**, representing relationships that may interest both general audiences and serve as interpretative tools for scholars or domain experts. Indeed, uncovering hidden relationships and giving life to raw data underlies the essence of meaningful visualization.

A significant shift in how scholars approach **quantitative visualizations** emerged with Franco Moretti's "*Graphs, Maps, Trees*" (Moretti 2005). Moretti introduced the concept of **distant reading** for textual data, transforming traditional literary studies by proposing the use of **graphs** and **maps** to explore textual corpora. While **close reading** focuses on individual texts—such as analyzing style, iconography, or marginalia—distant reading shifts the viewpoint from the particular to global features, enabling scholars to generate high-level insights and detect broader trends across datasets. Today, this distinction also applies to annotations in digital and collaborative environments: close reading can entail detailed examinations of individual visual artworks or manuscripts, whereas distant reading may identify overarching patterns or connections in extensive collections of annotated materials.

Meanwhile, GLAM institutions have increasingly digitized their inventories in pursuit of meaningful digital representations of their collections. However, despite the expanding variety of cultural collection visualizations (Windhager et al., 2019) scientific data representation techniques still dominate. Nonetheless the application of these scientific methods to humanistic data has repeatedly faced resistance, particularly since Moretti's publication, both on scholars' side (Marche 2012) (Goodwin and Holbo 2011) and from visual researchers such as Johanna Drucker (2011, 2016) who criticize the uncritical transfer of these methods into the humanities, emphasizing that many visualizations neglect humanistic concerns like interpretation, ambiguity, uncertainty, and

⁸⁴ <https://giorgialupi.com/data-humanism-my-manifesto-for-a-new-data-world>

perspectival specificity. The next chapter will thus analyze the possibilities and challenges in visualizing CH data.

4.1 Visualizing data in the Humanities

Visualizations that offer broad overviews can reveal large-scale patterns across datasets (Shneiderman 1996). However, such approaches often fail to capture the intricate relations at the level of individual items. Moreover, relying on a single viewpoint can omit critical context, leading to distorted or overly simplistic interpretations. Given that relational and contextual connections are as crucial as high-level trends—particularly in CH data—there is considerable benefit in employing visualization methods that illuminate multifaceted data.

Metadata: The Cornerstone of CH Visualization

A survey by Windhager et al. (2019) indicates that digital collections typically include two main data types: (1) **the content** that constitutes the digital cultural object and (2) **the accompanying metadata** describing or contextualizing the object.

Because CH objects vary widely in scope, quality, and structure across institutions, standardized models like the **Europeana Data Model (EDM)**⁸⁵ have been developed. EDM supports two complementary approaches:

- Object-centric: Emphasizes static attributes (e.g., creator, date, type, location), alongside contextual relationships (actors, places, events, ontologies).
- Event-centric: Builds more relational structures by linking objects, agents, and contextual entities through events at specific times and places.

Although the object-centric method is more prevalent, event-centric modeling can offer nuanced relational networks or hierarchies. Metadata for CH objects may range from simple textual descriptions (free-form text or structured keywords) to numerical attributes (e.g., creation years) and multimedia content (images, audio, video, 3D models). While many CH visualizations remain metadata-driven, some also incorporate direct content representations (images or book covers) or employ data enrichment techniques (text mining, shape clustering, style classification). Despite ongoing challenges, metadata is crucial for representing, analyzing, and visualizing CH collections.

Datafication Strategies in GLAM Institutions

⁸⁵ <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/edm-documentation>

According to Windhager et al. (2019b), GLAM institutions typically adopt three main datafication strategies:

1. Reusing Existing Metadata

Incorporates structured metadata (e.g., date, origin, creator, category) or textual descriptions already linked to the cultural object (Baca 2003).

2. Extracting Structured Metadata

Derives metadata through computational techniques, such as natural language processing (Jänicke et al. 2017) or image recognition (Castellano and Vessio 2021). These methods make implicit features explicit and facilitate further analysis.

3. Generating New Annotation Layers

Adds computer-readable layers of information via annotations, enriching the object's context with additional data (Kleymann and Stange 2021).

These strategies inevitably involve uncertainty, a fundamental characteristic of humanistic data that distinguishes it from purely scientific data. Windhager et al. (2019b) identify several types of uncertainty—ranging from object (missing or lost items) to temporal (ambiguous dates), geospatial, set-typed (unclear categorical assignments), relational (contested links in networks), attribute (disputed metadata), and provenance (ownership or historical trajectory). Each type demands careful visualization approaches to capture imprecision without oversimplifying the dataset.

Many GLAM institutions may avoid fully disclosing uncertainty (e.g., incomplete digitization or inconsistent metadata) to minimize reputational risks. Additionally, the interface design challenge becomes more complex when attempting to represent data quality or uncertainty. Simplicity and consistency often take precedence, potentially hampering the adoption of more multi-dimensional or transparent visualizations.

Making uncertainty explicit can improve trust in both the system and its methods (Sacha et al. 2016). However, modeling and visualizing uncertainty also increases complexity in back-end data processes and front-end design. For traditional scholars, new uncertainty indicators may require learning additional tools or interpretive frameworks. For casual users, the added layers might diminish the entertainment or aesthetic value. Balancing scientific accuracy with usability remains a central tension in GLAM contexts, necessitating critical reflection on how best to present uncertainty.

Approaches to Visualizing CH Collections

The ongoing task of categorizing and comparing different information visualization solutions for CH data remains an active research area (Windhager et al. 2019). While the event-centric approach can establish richer relational insights by linking objects to actors, places, and times, the object-centric model still dominates in most DH projects—often anchored in metadata describing each item (image, audio, video, text, or 3D object).

Interaction with CH collections in physical galleries usually entails close-up observation or browsing from object to object. In digital formats, these possibilities broaden to include distant perspectives. Greene and colleagues conceptualize the information visualization design space by distinguishing between previews (visual surrogates for individual objects) and overviews (representations of entire collections) (Greene et al. 2000). These further break down into:

1. Single Object Previews – High-resolution images, 3D scans, videos, or audio recordings, typically paired with metadata.
2. Multi-Object Previews – Aggregations in lists, grids, or mosaics, often resulting from search queries or faceted browsing.
3. Collection Overviews with Discrete Surrogates – Macro-level layouts where each object is shown as an individual glyph encoding metadata.
4. Collection Overviews with Abstractions – Diagrammatic representations that abstract away from individual items, emphasizing broad patterns through geometric shapes.

The survey (Windhager et al. 2019) indicate over half of the studied information visualization systems incorporate full object previews, about 60% provide multi-object previews, and around 75% include some form of collection overview—split between those using discrete representations and those applying diagrammatic abstractions. This varied landscape reflects the dual need to facilitate close study of objects while also empowering distant analyses of entire collections.

Complexity and Uncertainty in Cultural Data

Scholars in the humanities have long utilized visual representation techniques—such as graphs and charts—for statistical displays, even though these methods originate in empirically grounded disciplines. This adoption, however, has not been without critique. Such visualizations often assume a realist epistemology, treating phenomena as observer-independent “data” that can be objectively captured and passively recorded. From a humanistic perspective, this mindset overlooks the interpretive and subjective foundations of knowledge production in the humanities.

By contrast, a humanistic perspective challenges this assumption by emphasizing the constructivist nature of knowledge. To reframe the discussion, Johanna Drucker (2011) introduces the distinction between “**data**” and “**capta**”. The term **data** implies a “given” (pre-existing) that exists

independently of the observer, whereas **capta** emphasizes that knowledge is “taken”, actively constructed, and shaped by interpretive acts. This distinction underscores the situated, partial, and constitutive nature of knowledge production in the humanities. From this perspective, the humanities do not simply observe and record the world but actively engage in its representation, acknowledging the subjective and interpretive nature of the process.

Consequently, visualizations aligned with humanistic inquiry must go beyond simply repurposing empirical tools. Instead, they require rethinking data as *capta* and designing visual frameworks that highlight uncertainty, ambiguity, and contextual specificity—in short, **the interpretive and constructed nature of knowledge**. Such an approach not only questions quantitative methods that claim authority through perceived certainty but also demands new visualization paradigms that can convey the complexities and situatedness central to humanistic scholarship.

The complexity of cultural data is not merely an outcome of their heterogeneous nature but also arises from the layered meanings and interpretations they carry. These layers are influenced by the historical, social, and cultural contexts in which the data were created and interpreted. Complexity, as explored across various disciplines such as systems theory and information science, is often characterized by interactions among numerous differentiated elements that lead to emergent, non-linear behaviors. This understanding is vital for cultural data, which frequently exhibit “unknowns” and “unknowables”, making simplistic representations inadequate. Uncertainty, another hallmark of humanistic data, stems from a variety of sources (Windhager et al. 2019b). Historical object information often contains accumulated guesses, estimates, or omissions from prior collectors and curators, introducing gaps and ambiguities that persist in the digital realm. Digitization processes further contribute to uncertainty, whether through OCR errors, transcription inaccuracies, or limitations in database creation. Feature extraction, relying on probabilistic algorithms, can also introduce variability, as computational recognition methods often generate results with inherent uncertainties. Human sensemaking and categorical annotation processes compound these challenges, embedding subjective interpretations into the data. Over time, these uncertainties propagate through representational systems, where design decisions in data modeling, processing, and visualization can either obscure or amplify the underlying ambiguities.

In an effort to mitigate these uncertainties, information visualization approaches for cultural collections encode multiple data dimensions into interactive forms—such as graphs, maps, timelines, or trees. These web-based interfaces can function as digital counterparts to physical cultural institutions, offering structured, mediated, and narrated access to collections. Nonetheless, while such systems facilitate insights, learning, and aesthetic exploration, they also risk concealing ambiguities inherent in the data.

Effective visualization strategies strive to communicate uncertainty without oversimplifying its complexities. Techniques like glyph variations, opacity adjustments, or interactive data-quality indicators can help users navigate data in ways that balance detailed insights with accessible overviews. These strategies must cater to both domain experts (who demand precision and depth) and casual users (who may prefer more straightforward, visually appealing experiences). By making uncertainty visible, cultural heritage systems can foster transparency and trust, supporting critical engagement and informed decision-making.

4.2 Multi-modal interfaces for the Cultural Heritage domain

Interfaces serve as the mediators between humans and digital systems, appearing in countless forms—whether in smartphones, dashboards, or even coffee machines. Initially studied within **Human-Computer Interaction (HCI)**, interfaces were largely task-oriented, designed to optimize usability by minimizing user frustration and maximizing efficiency. While this functionalist perspective has undoubtedly advanced interface design, it often reduces people to “users”, overlooking the interpretive depth and subjective dimensions central to humanities work.

A specialized category of interfaces—**Graphical User Interfaces (GUIs)**—dominates our screens and devices. They are considered one of the most transformative communication innovations in recent decades. Johanna Drucker (2011b, 2014) argues for a humanistic approach to interface design, suggesting that interfaces should be regarded as dynamic mediating spaces rather than static, fixed entities. This perspective aligns with the humanities’ emphasis on interpretation, contextual awareness, and cognitive provocation, framing users as subjects who engage in meaning-making rather than as mere operators completing tasks. According to Drucker, an interface is both what we read and how we read, merging engagement with cognitive stimulation and functioning as an enunciative apparatus—a space where individuals construct identity and knowledge through interaction.

Since task optimization has dominated interface design—shaped by principles of web usability outlined by Jakob Nielsen⁸⁶—most interfaces prioritize information structures that align with user goals. Although this approach is useful, it often neglects how interfaces also shape self-constitution and subjectivity. From a humanistic standpoint, the subject’s engagement with an interface leaves a trace, which is fundamental to cultural and cognitive processes of self-recognition. Thus, a humanistic approach to interface design seeks to move beyond mere usability to illuminate deeper interpretive, relational, and symbolic dimensions.

⁸⁶ <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/ten-usability-heuristics/>

Viewing interfaces as ecologies, or border zones between human subjects and cultural systems, underscores how design can foster transformative interactions. A **subject-oriented approach** acknowledges the interplay of cultural, cognitive, and representational factors. It recognizes that an interface's structure can influence how a subject navigates knowledge, interprets data, and constructs meaning.

The Dynamic Nature of Web Environments

Unlike static media (e.g., printed books), web environments are inherently modular and mutable. Users navigate multiple levels of content—texts, images, videos, interactive graphs—shifting between ephemeral “pages” or “frames” whose organization can be quickly rearranged. Such fluidity offers opportunities for distant reading (in the sense advocated by Franco Moretti) and multi-level analysis, but it also requires new strategies for structuring and interpreting large, heterogeneous datasets.

For scholars, these dynamic modalities change how “reading” occurs. Traditional notions of *text* and *paratext* expand into networks of frames, hyperlinked references, and adjustable visual scales (e.g., zooming in/out, drilling down, or collapsing sections). As a result, the cognitive processes and subject positions invoked by such interfaces differ substantially from those associated with linear textual experiences. Digital interfaces frequently adopt mathematical or spatial structures (e.g., networks, graphs, hierarchical views) to organize content. However, these same structures, while efficient, can unintentionally impose cognitive constraints, subtly guiding how users interpret or value information. As Drucker explains, graphical organization does not inherently produce effects; rather, it provokes responses by ordering the conditions of meaning-making. Emphasizing the term “subject” over “user” highlights this dependence: cognition and interpretation are shaped by the representational system in which they take place. Accordingly, interface theory must extend from subject theory, questioning the purely engineering-focused perspective of traditional HCI. This reconceptualization makes room for interpretive depth, focusing on the ways visual hierarchies, semantic groupings, and narrative flows in interfaces influence understanding and user engagement.

Despite the flexibility of digital environments, many web layouts still emulate the rectangular frames inherited from print culture. These design conventions reflect deep-seated reading habits rather than any strict technological necessity. Modern devices have begun incorporating more intuitive interactions—zooming, scaling, or panning—through tactile interfaces, moving closer to the conceptual ideal of a fluid and reconfigurable “page”.

Historical examples, such as the Talmudic page⁸⁷, highlight how textual layout can encode communal knowledge and interpretative practices, with marginal notes and commentaries creating a multi-layered reading experience. These precedents illuminate how a page (or screen) can serve as a site of mediation, reflecting community-specific codes and forging a collective identity through shared interpretative conventions. In the digital realm, this insight suggests that interface design must embrace the complexities of textual tradition, rethinking how annotations, references, or commentary shape collective understanding.

Because digital repositories often contain massive amounts of data, new approaches are necessary for both distant reading and close inspection. Multiple “tables of contents”—derived from text, metadata, or database structures—can be combined with semantic web diagrams linking entities (names, locations, motifs). This duality between distant overviews and detailed object previews nurtures a flexible scholarly navigation.

Concepts such as serendipity and generous interfaces (drawn from library and information sciences) highlight the potential for unexpected discoveries. Interfaces can facilitate these encounters by revealing related artifacts or contexts and proposing surprising paths that spark intellectual curiosity. Similarly, collaborative modalities—akin to online gaming—enable multiple participants to share interpretive trails and viewpoints, blending argumentation with navigation in a socially embedded discourse space.

In this framework, interface design does more than simply deliver content; it actively shapes how subjects engage with, interpret, and build upon cultural heritage data. A focus on interpretation, ambiguity, and transformation moves interfaces beyond functional constraints, empowering users to explore the multifaceted dimensions of humanistic knowledge.

Toward a Subject-Oriented Interface Theory

Building on Johanna Drucker’s insights, a **subject-oriented** interface design approach moves beyond task-based usability to foreground the **interpretive** and **constitutive roles of individuals**. Every interface embodies a point-of-view system, shaping how content is perceived, navigated, and understood. Analogous to perspectival systems in art, digital interfaces position users within specific representational frameworks that influence cognition and meaning-making.

Rather than treating the interface as a neutral “delivery system”, a subject-oriented approach views it as an epistemic space. In this space, the user not only consumes content but also actively co-constructs it. **Engaging with metadata, cross-links, and annotations, users transform raw data into**

⁸⁷ <https://jewishmuseum.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/Talmud-example-page.pdf>

personalized knowledge. This paradigm challenges interface designers to prioritize interpretative plurality, cultural specificity, and community-building over one-size-fits-all efficiency. It underscores the idea that interfaces are cultural artifacts themselves, shaping—and shaped by—our collective modes of inquiry, discourse, and self-constitution.

Drucker (2014) emphasizes that every interface embodies a point of view system—a structured relationship between the subject and the representation of the world within the interface. Just as perspectival systems in art position a stationary viewer with a defined cone of vision or orthographic systems assume equal distances to the object, digital interfaces inherently position users within specific representational frameworks. These frameworks not only structure how users perceive and interact with content but also influence their cognitive and interpretative processes.

In this context, a subject-oriented design approach seeks to foreground the situated nature of the user’s engagement. It recognizes that interfaces are spaces where users produce and are produced by their interactions with the system. Whether through the spatial organization of screen elements, the framing of visual hierarchies, or the interplay of data-driven and subjective insights, interfaces act as mediating structures that reflect and shape the user’s understanding of the world.

Drucker’s insights challenge designers to rethink the role of interfaces in cultural heritage and digital humanities. By designing for interpretative plurality and acknowledging the constitutive role of users, interfaces can evolve from functional tools into epistemic spaces that foster deeper engagement, critical inquiry, and the co-construction of knowledge.

4.3 Semiotics and Hermeneutics of Annotations

Semiotics and **hermeneutics** are two major theoretical frameworks that deepen our understanding of how meaning is embedded, interpreted, and communicated in texts and signs. Semiotics examines the nature and function of signs, whereas hermeneutics focuses on the interpretation of texts.

Sometimes referred to as semiology, semiotics investigates how signs, symbols, and their interpretations shape meaning. It encompasses the analysis of sign processes (semiosis)—activities, behaviors, or processes in which signs play a role. A sign is defined broadly as anything (e.g., word, image, gesture, object) that communicates meaning to an interpreter. The field seeks to explain how this meaning is created and conveyed.

One of the discipline’s seminal figures, the Swiss linguist Ferdinand de Saussure, described semiotics as studying the *“life of signs in society”*. The meaning of a sign can be intended or unintended, depending on both the nature of the sign and the intentions of its creator. While semiotics has not always been formally institutionalized as an academic discipline, it draws on a variety of theoretical

perspectives and methodological approaches. Umberto Eco (1976), for instance, famously stated that semiotics “*is concerned with everything that can be taken as a sign*”. In this sense, anything that “stands for” something else—words, images, sounds, gestures, or objects—can be studied semiotically, underscoring the field’s inherently interdisciplinary nature.

Hermeneutics is traditionally associated with interpreting religious scriptures, such as the Bible and the Quran, yet its scope extends well beyond sacred texts. Central to hermeneutics is understanding an author’s intent and revealing the objective meaning of a text, rather than merely relying on subjective impressions. This process considers a text’s historical, grammatical, linguistic, rhetorical, and contextual dimensions, as well as its canonical status, to fully grasp its significance. Beyond textual interpretation, hermeneutics also applies to **visual language**, which includes designs that manifest contours, volumes, and compositions on surfaces. These visuals embody dichotomies such as up/down, inside/outside, big/small, or allowed/prohibited, shaping how people conceptualize their environment. Over time, hermeneutics has evolved through diverse schools of thought, each offering interpretive frameworks shaped by specific historical and cultural circumstances.

This universality of interpretation is captured in Stuart’s observation that “*all the human races are, and ever have been, interpreters. It is a law of their rational, intelligent, communicative nature*” (Stuart 1834). Thus, hermeneutics extends beyond textual realms to offer insight into semiotic and symbolic systems intrinsic to visual representations, making it highly relevant to the study of annotations—whether textual or visual.

Bringing semiotics and hermeneutics together illuminates how annotations function as signs within a broader interpretive framework. Annotations in digital or scholarly contexts often consist of textual notes, visual markers, or symbolic cues that guide interpretation and deepen understanding. By applying semiotic analysis, we can see how signs within an annotation carry both intended and potentially unintended meanings, influencing how content is perceived. Meanwhile, hermeneutic principles emphasize the interpretive act—the historical, cultural, and contextual forces that shape how a reader or viewer unpacks those signs.

In practice, these theoretical insights encourage both designers and scholars to consider:

- **Contextual Clarity:** Ensuring that annotations explicitly reference their source, creator, date, and interpretive intent to enable accurate hermeneutic analysis.
- **Sign Variability:** Recognizing that an annotation might function differently depending on user background and symbolic literacy.
- **Iterative Interpretation:** Allowing annotations to be revisited or revised over time, aligning with hermeneutics’ emphasis on evolving understanding.

- **Visual and Textual Integration:** Designing annotation systems that seamlessly combine text, images, or other media, accommodating the semiotic premise that signs can take many forms.

Ultimately, a deep appreciation of both semiotic processes (how signs generate meaning) and hermeneutic processes (how those meanings are interpreted within contexts) can guide the development of prototype annotations and visualization tools that better reflect the layered complexity of cultural artifacts.

4.3.1 From interpretation to argumentation

What applies to literary studies can also extend to visual studies and related fields in the humanities. As Kleymann and Stange (2021) note, scholars engage in several key activities: interpretation, the development and application of theories and methods, and argumentation. After identifying the signs and contexts through semiotic and hermeneutic principles, scholars often move toward argumentation to validate or contest interpretative claims within a broader theoretical framework.

Interpretation ranks among the primary tasks in literary studies (Albrecht et al. 2015), yet it also underpins inquiry in the digital humanities more generally—particularly when dealing with annotations. As Nünning and Nünning (2010) explain, a literary theory is an explicit, systematic set of categories for describing or explaining aspects of a text. A method is the procedural approach used to acquire knowledge; a single theory may encompass multiple methods, from deductive or dialectical to open-ended processes like reading or generating hypotheses.

Argumentation, described by Cicero in “*De Partitione Oratoria*” as the “*unfolding of given proofs*” (Rädle 2000, 130–132), is the common thread that binds these interpretative acts. In both literary studies and fields such as iconology or visual semiotics, the process of generating and validating interpretations relies on the ability to present coherent arguments grounded in established methods and theories. When applied to annotation systems, this perspective means that annotations can function not just as notes but as structured arguments—where each note references its theoretical basis, clarifies the method used, and invites scholarly debate. By building clear, logical arguments, researchers contribute to a richer, more dialogic understanding of textual or visual materials.

4.3.2 Semiology of graphics

Semiology of graphics, as explored by Jacques Bertin in his seminal work “*Sémiologie Graphique*” (1967), offers a systematic approach to visualizing information through signs and symbols. By leveraging fundamental properties of human perception, graphic representations allow viewers to encode and decode complex data at a glance. Unlike polysemic systems—such as figurative art or cinematographic representations—that invite multiple interpretations, the monosemic structure of

graphics aims for precision and clarity of communication, making it invaluable for tasks that require unambiguous data interpretation.

Bertin emphasized that graphics serve a dual purpose: they function both as a storage mechanism for preserving knowledge and as a research tool for uncovering relationships and patterns within data. This approach is especially significant in disciplines like cartography, topography, and data visualization, where the scope of representation can range from microscopic structures to astronomical phenomena. Unlike linear forms of notation (e.g., verbal or musical sequences), graphic representations are spatial and allow viewers to discern complex relationships instantaneously.

Bertin's Visual Variables

Central to Bertin's model are **seven fundamental visual variables** that underpin effective graphic representation. These variables can be manipulated to convey both qualitative and quantitative information, thereby anchoring much of modern visualization design:

1. **Location:** Defines the position of a symbol within a coordinate system. Location is considered indispensable for spatial representation, as it determines how data points are related geographically or within a conceptual framework.
2. **Size:** Refers to the area or volume occupied by a symbol. Variations in size often communicate quantitative differences, as seen in proportional symbol maps or flow diagrams.
3. **Shape:** Describes the external form of a symbol, ranging from geometric shapes like circles or squares to more iconic forms that directly mimic the objects they represent. Shape is essential for categorizing qualitative data.
4. **Orientation:** Represents the direction or rotation of a symbol. Orientation is often used in flow maps to depict movement or directionality and in multivariate glyphs to differentiate attributes.
5. **Color hue:** Encodes data using variations in wavelength, such as blue, green, or red. Color hue is effective for distinguishing nominal categories or classes, particularly in choropleth maps.
6. **Color value:** Refers to the relative lightness or darkness of a symbol, often used to indicate hierarchical or quantitative differences through shading.
7. **Texture:** Denotes the density or pattern within a symbol. Texture is frequently employed to convey intensity or variability within datasets, such as in dot-density maps.

Subsequent scholars have expanded Bertin's framework to accommodate the evolving landscape of digital visualization. Roth (2017), for instance, identifies additional variables that reflect modern cartographic and computational methods:

8. **Color saturation:** Indicates the vividness or purity of a color, distinguishing bold, saturated symbols from pastel or desaturated ones. This variable is particularly useful for emphasizing data points in thematic maps.
9. **Arrangement:** Refers to the spatial layout of symbols, from regular, grid-like patterns to irregular, clustered arrangements. Arrangement is often manipulated in dot-density maps to highlight spatial distributions.
10. **Crispness:** Relates to the sharpness or fuzziness of a symbol's boundary. Crispness is particularly effective for visualizing uncertainty, as sharper boundaries suggest higher confidence in the data.
11. **Resolution:** Describes the level of detail in a symbol, whether through the granularity of raster grids or the precision of vector linework. High-resolution symbols convey greater specificity, while lower resolutions emphasize general trends.
12. **Transparency:** Reflects the degree of blending between a symbol and its background or overlapping elements. Transparency is used to layer data, making it particularly effective in multi-dimensional visualizations.

Figure 15 - Visual Variables and their syntactics. Based on Bertin (1967/1983), MacEachren (1995), and MacEachren et al. (2012). (Source: Roth, Robert., 2017, "Visual Variables.")

Bertin also stressed the active role of the interpreter. Graphics are not passively received; rather, users engage with elements, extracting meaning and forming relationships based on their own cultural and contextual backgrounds. Semiotics reinforces this view by linking visual variables to signification processes (e.g., a map symbol [signifier] representing a geographic feature [signified], interpreted by a user [interpretant]). Moreover, Bertin posited that these visual variables operate at the “retinal” level: they are pre-attentive, meaning they are perceived almost immediately by the eye and brain, without requiring extensive cognitive processing. This concept underpins the effectiveness of well-designed maps, charts, and other visualizations, which rely on visually salient cues for conveying information.

Bertin categorized visual variables by how they shape user perception, identifying four levels of visual organization:

- **Associative Perception:** Associative variables allow the viewer to perceive all variations in the visual scene as a unified group, with no single variation dominating. For example, in Figure 16a, variations in color hue are perceived equally, creating horizontal rows, while Figure 16b shows a similar effect using variations in shape. Bertin classified location, shape, orientation, color hue, and texture as associative variables, as they permit attention to other elements of the visual scene.
- **Dissociative Perception:** Dissociative variables, in contrast, dominate the viewer's attention, drawing focus to specific variations. For example, in Figure 16c, darker color values stand out against a white background, creating a vertical gradient. Similarly, in Figure 16d, variations in size draw the eye to larger symbols, overriding the perception of horizontal rows seen in associative examples. This dominance can inhibit attention to other visual variables in the same scene. Bertin believed size and color value to be dissociative variables.
- **Selective Perception:** Selective variables enable the viewer to isolate a specific category or variation within the visual scene while ignoring others. For instance, in Figure 16e, the distribution of red symbols is easily discerned, while Figure 16f shows that identifying hexagonal shapes is less intuitive. This demonstrates that color hue is more effective for selective perception than shape, which Bertin argued is the only visual variable that is not selective.
- **Ordered and Quantitative Perception:** Ordered variables allow variations to be perceived as ranked or hierarchical, with one variation seen as “more” or “less” than another. For instance, in Figure 16e, green symbols are perceived as different but not as hierarchically “more” than purple symbols, while in Figure 16g, darker symbols suggest greater intensity compared to lighter ones. Quantitative variables extend this concept, enabling numerical estimation. For example, Figure 16h illustrates how variations in size allow viewers to estimate relative quantities with the aid of a legend. Bertin considered location and size to be the most effective quantitative variables. Later researchers, such as MacEachren (1995), expanded this to include color saturation, crispness, resolution, and transparency, while arguing that texture is only marginally ordered.

Figure 16 - Visual Variables Level of Organization based on Bertin (1967/1983). (Source: Roth, Robert., 2017, "Visual Variables.")

Subsequent scholars, including MacEachren (1995), refined Bertin's views by classifying visual variables as good, marginal, or poor for nominal, ordinal, and numerical data, respectively—further aligning them with the measurement level of the data.

In cartography and information visualization, syntactics refers to the relationships among signs, determining how well a chosen visual variable fits the data's measurement level:

- **Nominal information (categorical data):** Best encoded using unordered variables like color hue, shape, or orientation.
- **Ordinal information (ranked data):** Encoded using ordered but non-quantitative variables, such as color value, color saturation, or transparency.
- **Numerical information (quantitative data):** Requires quantitative variables like location and size, which can also encode ordinal and nominal data due to their visual dominance.

Jacques Bertin's semiology of graphics remains integral to modern data visualization, particularly in domains like cartography and cultural heritage. By identifying core visual variables and detailing how

they operate at the perceptual level, Bertin laid the groundwork for cognitively efficient displays of complex information. Ongoing research has expanded his original framework—introducing new variables and refining how best to map these variables to different data types. Ultimately, Bertin’s emphasis on visual perception and active interpretation resonates with semiotic and hermeneutic principles, underscoring the dynamic interplay between symbolic forms and user engagement.

5. VISTA: a Semantic Annotator Prototype for IIF

The VISTA⁸⁸ (Visual Interpretative Semantic Tagging Application) prototype was developed over the months, building on my internship experience at Net7 during the ProDEM project. This project involved a feasibility study on IIF, JSON-LD, and open-source annotation tools like Mirador, aiming to bridge design principles with DH technologies. The goal was to move beyond mere image visualization, enabling interpretation, discussion, and semantic enrichment through structured annotation.

The importance of technical knowledge in design is well articulated by Albe Steiner, who stresses the designer's responsibility to master both industrial production processes and technical methodologies:

*“Il grafico per poter intervenire nel processo di produzione moderna deve prima di tutto acquisire profonda conoscenza della sua responsabilità, deve studiare e conoscere i sistemi di produzione industriale che interessano la sua attività, deve essere padrone della tecnica di mestiere.”*⁸⁹ (Steiner 1978, 144)

This principle guided my approach in combining graphic design expertise with an in-depth understanding of IIF, Mirador, and semantic annotation models. Similarly, Bruno Munari highlights the collaborative nature of design, arguing that a designer works not for an élite but for collective problem-solving:

*“Il designer è un progettista dotato di senso estetico, che lavora per la comunità. Il suo non è un lavoro personale ma di gruppo: il designer organizza un gruppo di lavoro secondo il problema che deve risolvere.”*⁹⁰ (Munari 1971, 28).

This aligns with digital humanities methodologies, where scholars, developers, and domain experts collaborate on iterative and evolving digital projects.

Addressing the Gaps in Existing DH Annotation Tools

Existing DH visualization tools often treat data as a fixed entity, primarily focusing on representation rather than interpretation. Platforms like Recogito or Glycerine provide textual or geospatial

⁸⁸ <https://github.com/sterenz/VISTA>

⁸⁹ “In order to intervene in the modern production process, the graphic designer must, first of all, acquire a deep knowledge of his responsibility; he must study and know the industrial production systems that affect his activity; he must master the technical aspects of the profession.”

⁹⁰ “The designer is a technician with an aesthetic sense, who works for the community. His work is not personal but a group effort: the designer organizes a workgroup according to the problem to be solved.”

annotation, but lack robust structures for multi-level, interpretative engagement with visual data. Art-historical research, particularly iconographic and iconological analysis, requires a semantic framework that accommodates divergent viewpoints, evolving interpretations, and scholarly debate.

To address this, VISTA adopts Johanna Drucker's concept of the Two-Way Screen—an interface that not only displays data but actively integrates user interpretation (Drucker 2016). Rather than presenting static annotations, VISTA allows scholars to annotate, contest, and refine interpretations dynamically. In doing so, it aligns with hermeneutic principles, framing data not as pre-existing facts but as *capta*—constructed through interpretation (Drucker 2011).

VISTA introduces a multi-layered annotation paradigm, integrating IIIF with iconographic and iconological analysis based on established ontologies such as ICON. The prototype adheres to LOD and LOUD principles, ensuring interoperability, provenance tracking, and versioning capabilities for evolving scholarly discourse. By combining semiotic and hermeneutic insights with practical visualization strategies, VISTA aims to move beyond traditional annotation models, offering a dynamic, interpretation-driven interface for cultural heritage scholars.

5.1 Prototype design

The prototype design also draws on Johanna Drucker's work, particularly her notion of the “two-way screen” (see Figure 17), articulated during her presentation “Dimensions of Visualization for the Humanities” (Fachhochschule Potsdam, 2016) while presenting the 3DH project. While many digital humanities visualizations follow representational paradigms, treating data as a one-way flow onto the screen, Drucker proposes a model in which the screen also captures interpretative acts—effectively transforming data from a passive entity into *capta* (actively constructed knowledge).

Figure 17 - Conception of the Two-Way-Screen. (Source: Drucker, Johanna, 2016, “Draft originated in the 3DH project” - https://pages.gseis.ucla.edu/faculty/drucker/3DH_Gallery/TwoWayScreenx.jpg).

1. Representational Paradigm:

- Most existing interfaces rely on a data-driven display, focusing on efficiency and objective representation.
- They rarely accommodate interpretative or hermeneutic processes—especially in art-historical contexts where multi-level meaning (iconographic, iconological) is essential.

2. Two-Way Screen:

- Advocates a bidirectional environment, capturing user-driven modifications (annotations, changes, disagreements) as new data.
- Encourages an iterative cycle: users read visualizations for insights about the “whole” (the entire dataset or artwork) and refine the “part” (specific annotations), continuously generating new representations.

Methodology

The methodology behind the development of VISTA was inspired by a six-step process adapted from Drucker’s talk:

1. Defining the Problem (Big, Vague)

VISTA aims to be a community-focused application that facilitates art-historical annotation of digital images. Recognizing the semantic gap in existing annotation platforms—particularly for iconographic and iconological aspects—a first draft of the **LISA data model was developed to anchor the UI.**

2. Achieving Consensus in the Research Group

Although initially a thesis project, it involved continuous dialogue with domain experts to refine design goals. Through evaluation sessions and informal interviews, we concluded that many current visualizations remain limited by representational biases, lacking interpretative flexibility required by art historians.

3. Breaking the Problem into Smaller Tasks

We identified four core actions for the prototype:

- Creating an annotation for the Pre-Iconographical (first) level of recognition.
- Linking all three iconographic levels (Pre-Iconographical, Iconographical, Iconological).
- Adding a “disagree” annotation on the same target (to capture scholarly debate).
- Visualizing the entities and relations emerging from annotations.

Early prototypes, created in Figma, underwent internal sessions (akin to charettes) to test usability and data model validity.

4. Aligning Tasks with Expertise

Team discussions yielded a distinction between the “inside” (the working space for creating, modifying, saving visualizations) and the “outside” (infrastructure, community, institutional contexts). While connected, the prototype’s unique contribution lies in how it manages the “inside” to reflect hermeneutic principles.

5. Charettes and Testing Sessions

We ran iterative charettes, focusing on the user’s workflow, annotation steps, and the interface’s ability to reflect LISA’s semantic complexity. This led us to expand the LISA model to include additional ICON classes and properties, thereby reinforcing the UI’s multi-level recognition capacity.

6. Setting Milestones and Realistic Workflows

We integrated insights from art-historical practice, acknowledging that image-based annotation is a fundamental method. By leveraging IIF’s JSON-based structure, we ensured both interoperability and straightforward data sharing. Additional expansions included role management (via PRO) for collaboration, disagreement handling (via HiCO), and provenance tracking (via PROV-O), aligning with advanced scholarly requirements.

5.1.1 Information Architecture

The underlying architecture of VISTA is centered around a primary entity: the **Collection**. After signing in (or logging in), users can either create a new collection of annotations or continue working on an existing one. The navigation system is designed for simplicity, ensuring that all key sections remain at the same hierarchical level in the first layer of navigation.

During the initial interactions with the wireframe, it became evident that a structured organization model was needed to facilitate collaborative annotation efforts within a working group. To address this, VISTA organizes annotations—created on different Canvases and sourced from various IIF Manifests—into Collections. This structural decision was also incorporated into the data model, where annotation pages (which list annotations on a given Canvas) are grouped within an annotation collection, leveraging the WADM class `oa:AnnotationCollection`.

Figure 18 - VISTA - Information architecture.

This approach enables better management, retrieval, and contextualization of annotations across different manifests and digital resources, providing a scalable framework for scholarly collaboration. Figure 18 illustrates the information architecture that guided the prototype design.

5.1.2 Basic user flow

To support the design process, a basic user flow was developed to outline the key steps in creating multi-level annotations following the three levels of recognition model (Pre-Iconographical, Iconographical, and Iconological).

Figure 19 - VISTA - User flow: "Create three level of annotations".

This flowchart accounts for several essential considerations:

- **Collection Management:** The system first checks whether the user has already created a collection. If not, they are prompted to create a new one.
- **Manifest Integration:** Once a collection exists, the system determines if a IIIF Manifest has been added. If not, the user can import a Manifest URL via the Mirador interface, ensuring access to the Canvas they intend to annotate.
- **Pre-Iconographical Annotations:** Users draw annotations directly on the Mirador interface, leveraging the Mirador Annotation extension to create Pre-Iconographical annotations (basic formal recognition of visual elements).
- **Annotation Management and Expansion:** After the initial annotation phase, the system enables users to manage and refine their annotations. This includes:
 - Adding higher levels of recognition (Iconographical and Iconological) to contextualize the identified elements.
 - Establishing semantic connections between different annotations, linking them hierarchically or relationally.
 - Expanding upon recognition layers, for example:
 - A Pre-Iconographical annotation may identify a figure in the painting.

- The Iconographical layer then specifies the subject.
- The Iconological layer provides interpretative depth.

5.1.3 Mock-Up

Select or Create a Collection

Upon authentication, the user enters the VISTA application and is presented with two options (see Figure 20):

- **Select Collection:** Continue working on an existing collection of annotations
- **New Collection:** Create a new collection from scratch

Figure 20 - VISTA - Select or create a new Collection.

The application's design prioritizes usability and flexibility, ensuring that users can seamlessly return to ongoing work or initiate new annotation projects as needed.

While the current prototype does not include a built-in authentication system, its design anticipates the need for user identity management and role-based access control in future iterations. A dedicated database would be required to handle user authentication, roles, and permissions, ensuring structured collaboration among multiple contributors.

Since the LISA data model considers different roles within a shared annotation environment, future implementations should establish the connection between users and the semantic roles defined in the model. Different roles would correspond to specific permissions that regulate interactions with annotations.

For example:

- A Publisher role should have the ability to change the annotation status, transitioning it from a Draft (the default state) to Published, or marking it as Deprecated if it is rejected.
- A Contributor role may be limited to creating and editing annotations, without the ability to modify their publication status.

While authentication and user management are not part of the current implementation, these aspects should be carefully considered in future developments to ensure controlled collaboration, versioning, and clear attribution of contributions.

When creating a new collection, the user is required to:

1. Enter a name for the collection.
2. Add collaborators who will participate in the annotation process.

The management of members and roles always remains accessible through the collection settings. This ensures that users can modify collaborators, adjust their roles, or remove participants as needed, even after the collection has been created.

Once these actions are completed, the user can proceed by adding the first IIF Manifest to the collection using Mirador's “+ Start Here” button, which allows users to paste the URL of a IIF Manifest from any external source and open it within the Mirador viewer (see Figure 21). This enables direct interaction with digital canvases, preparing them for annotation.

Figure 21 - VISTA - Create new collection and add a IIF Manifest

If a collection already exists, the user can continue working on an annotation campaign by selecting one of the previously added Manifests from the list (see Figure 22). This allows users to seamlessly pick up where they left off, ensuring continuity in the annotation process.

Figure 22 - VISTA - Select an existing Collection and select an already annotated IIF Manifest.

Create Annotations: Mirador UI redesign

Once a Manifest has been added or selected from the list, the user can begin annotating. To enhance usability and streamline the annotation process, a redesign of the existing Mirador annotation interface was implemented. The Mirador Annotation plugin already provides basic annotation functionalities, supporting both reading and writing annotations. However, several improvements were made to increase clarity and optimize the user experience.

Mirador natively supports reading annotations, displaying them in a left sidebar as a structured list. The Mirador Annotation plugin, on the other hand, extends this capability by allowing users to create new annotations. However, the existing UI presented usability challenges—particularly in the visibility of the annotation creation button. To improve this, the “+” icon button was redesigned to be more prominent, making the primary action of adding annotations immediately clear to users by adding the label “New” and the primary color to the button.

Figure 23 - VISTA - Annotated Canvas.

In the example below (see Figure 23) an annotation is already present on the Canvas and it is shown in the annotations list on the left sidebar. The annotation item list is a crucial element of the Mirador UI, providing an overview of all existing annotations on a given Canvas. In the redesigned interface, this list was improved to display useful metadata about each annotation, enhancing clarity and efficiency for users (see Figure 24).

Figure 24 - VISTA - Annotation item.

- **Annotation Status Indicator:** Each annotation now displays a color-coded status indicator on the left side of the item, helping users quickly identify its current stage:
 - Orange for Draft
 - Green for Published
 - Gray for Deprecated
- **Author Information:** The name of the annotation’s author is prominently displayed at the top of each item. In the example, we see “Jane Doe” as the creator of the annotation.

- **Recognition Level Label:** Each annotation is categorized according to its level of recognition (Pre-Iconographic, Iconographic, Iconological). This label appears as a color-coded tag in the top-right corner of the annotation item.

The color of the label matches the fill and stroke color of the annotation drawn on the Mirador Canvas, creating a visual mapping that aids interface readability.

In the example, the yellow label corresponds to the annotation’s yellow fill and stroke, reinforcing an intuitive link between the annotation’s visual representation and its metadata. These improvements were designed to ensure a seamless and efficient annotation workflow, reducing cognitive load and helping users quickly interpret and manage annotations in the Mirador interface.

Creating Pre-Iconographical annotations in Mirador

Continuing the redesign of the preexisting Mirador Annotation UI, another crucial feature is the right sidebar, which opens upon clicking the newly redesigned add button “+ New” button to create a new Pre-Iconographic annotation.

The annotation panel was redesigned with a key focus on enhancing the semantic layer of the annotation process, ensuring that every annotation creates a true entity that aligns with the LISA data model while maintaining the necessary level of semantic correctness (see Figure 25).

Figure 25 - VISTA - Sidebar for creation of Pre-Iconographical annotation.

To achieve this, the sidebar interface now includes structured text fields that allow users to either:

- Manually enter a value, or
- Select from a predefined list of options.

In the first interaction, after the user draws the annotation using one of the available tools (square, circle, polygon, or freehand tool), the system prompts them to define the type of element they are recognizing in the artwork.

Following the ICON ontology, which has been integrated into the LISA data model, the system recognizes three primary Pre-Iconographic annotation types:

- Natural Element – Objects or elements depicted in the image (e.g., tree, horse, column).
- Action – Human or non-human activities occurring in the image (e.g., running, embracing, pointing).
- Expressional Quality – The emotional, stylistic, or atmospheric characteristics conveyed in the image (e.g., solemnity, dynamism, serenity).

To aid user comprehension, contextual labels in the form of guiding questions are placed below the text fields or dropdown menus. Additionally, placeholder text within each field suggests examples or expected input formats, making the interface more intuitive.

Furthermore, to provide on-the-fly assistance, an information button (represented by an “i” icon inside a circle) is positioned next to each label. Clicking this button triggers a pop-up tooltip that offers detailed explanations of the selected recognition category. This feature proved particularly useful during user tests. Notably, even among domain experts, there was no unanimous agreement on the clarity of subject divisions proposed by ICON (i.e., Natural Element, Action, and Expressional Quality) and their implementation in the VISTA UI.

During the feasibility study, an important task was to implement conditional color filling and stroke variations based on the level of recognition. The ability to draw directly on the IIF Canvas is a significant feature already present in the original annotation plugin. However, the goal of VISTA was to visually represent the recognition level by enhancing the annotation’s appearance. The objective was to create a clear and intuitive visual system that distinctly highlighted what has been annotated, which was not sufficiently clear when using only a stroke as the default setting.

A solid fill would have obscured the underlying image, making it unreadable. After testing various scenarios, including cases with a high density of overlapping annotations, an optimal level of transparency was established. This solution not only ensures annotations remain clearly visible while preserving the artwork’s readability, but also provides a visual indicator of annotation density, effectively creating a heat map-like effect (see Figure 26).

Figure 26 - Study on the target color.

A further step involved assigning distinct colors to each recognition level. This choice was then consistently applied throughout the entire design, ensuring uniformity across various UI components, such as the annotation item list, where the recognition level is indicated through color coding.

After drawing the annotation and filling in the right sidebar form, the user can save the annotation, which will then appear in the left sidebar within the annotation list (see Figure 27).

Figure 27 - VISTA - Create Pre-Iconographical annotation.

Creating Iconographical Recognitions

The creation of higher levels of recognition was initially conceived within the same environment, allowing users to annotate all three levels directly in Mirador. However, this approach soon proved inconsistent, as multiple overlapping areas would have been drawn in nearly the same—but not precisely identical—locations. More critically, to align with the semantic structure of the model, it was necessary to establish explicit hierarchical relationships between the three levels of recognition. Since Pre-Iconographical Recognition is the first level, directly tied to the digital image itself, managing the higher levels separately within a dedicated section of the application ensured a clearer and more structured annotation process.

This separation also anticipates future developments in automated recognition, in which computer vision techniques can detect Pre-Iconographical elements, while scholars enrich these findings with higher-level interpretations. This human-in-the-loop approach preserves scholarly rigor while leveraging computational efficiency.

From a visualization perspective, this design choice aligns with Johanna Drucker's argument that **data visualization should not only represent information but also actively facilitate interpretation and knowledge production**. Rather than simply displaying annotations, VISTA enables users to create interpretative relationships by drawing connections between different levels of recognition. This shift transforms the tool from a static display of annotations into an interactive environment where scholars construct meaning through their interactions with the interface.

Within this section, three columns represent the three levels of recognition, displaying previously created annotations. Since the IIIF Canvas serves as the foundational object for these annotations, a dropdown menu positioned above the columns allows users to select which Canvas they wish to manage. By default, the initially selected Canvas is displayed. A future implementation aims to extend this feature to visualize the entire annotation set at the Collection level, enabling a broader, interconnected analysis across multiple Canvases (see Figure 28).

Figure 28 - VISTA - Manage Annotations section.

The creation of an Iconographical-level annotation is initiated by clicking the “+ Add recognition” button under the central column. Notably, the Iconological column remains inactive until at least one second-level recognition is present. This workflow constraint is intentionally designed to guide users through a structured, linear annotation process, ensuring a logical progression from Pre-Iconographical to Iconographical, and finally to Iconological Recognition.

The interface design of this section draws inspiration from task management applications, where cards are used to represent entities—in this case, annotations. These cards are organized spatially into three columns and distinguished visually by color:

- Yellow for Pre-Iconographical Recognition
- Magenta for Iconographical Recognition
- Purple for Iconological Recognition (inactive when no prior level is present)

The annotation creation process is facilitated through a pop-up form (see Figure 29), which structures user input in a guided manner.

Figure 29 - VISTA - Add Iconographical recognition.

As shown in the example, the pop-up form is displayed in its initial state (left) and after completion (right). To ensure semantic consistency with the underlying data model, the UI explicitly reflects the annotation categories defined in ICON and implemented in LISA. Users can select the appropriate subject category from:

- Character
- Place
- Event
- Named Object
- Symbol
- Personification

To assist users, an information icon (“i”) is available, providing contextual explanations when necessary.

A critical feature of VISTA is its ability to capture and represent uncertainty and provenance. To achieve this, each annotation field (subject name and type, reconciliation with external resources, and justification of recognition) is supplemented with provenance indicators:

- Subject identification: Includes the name and category of the recognized subject.
- External reconciliation: Allows linking to authoritative resources such as Wikidata, VIAF, and other controlled vocabularies.

- Justification: If the recognition is based on bibliographic sources, users can paste an external URI (e.g., links to scholarly books or articles supporting the iconographical interpretation).

To encourage completeness, each of these three components is visually tracked on the left side of the form. As fields are filled, green circles are progressively marked, providing visual feedback and guiding users toward a fully documented recognition. When all three macro fields are completed, a checkmark appears on the annotation card, confirming its validity.

Creating Iconographical Recognitions

Similar to the process of adding Iconographical Recognitions, users can create Iconological Recognitions in the rightmost column of the “Manage Annotations” section. However, an Iconological Recognition can only be added once at least one Iconographical Recognition has been defined. This stepwise approach ensures a structured workflow and maintains the hierarchical nature of interpretation.

Like the Iconographical Recognition process, the Iconological Recognition is added via a guided pop-up form (see Figure 30). Unlike the previous levels, the model currently defines a single category for Iconological Recognition—Composition. This simplification allows for a streamlined approach but may be expanded in future iterations to include additional semantic layers for more granular analysis.

Figure 30 - VISTA - Create Iconological recognition.

Visualizing the Three Levels in Mirador

Once all three levels of recognition have been created in the “Manage Annotations” section (see Figure 31), they can also be displayed directly within the Mirador interface (see Figure 32). This functionality integrates the structured annotations with the IIIF visualization environment, reinforcing the connection between the semantic model and the digital image representation.

Figure 31 - VISTA - Three level of recognition in Manage Annotations section.

Figure 32 - VISTA - Visualization of three level of recognition in Mirador.

Connecting Annotations Across Recognition Levels

Fundamental feature of the annotation manager is the ability to explicitly define relationships between different levels of recognition. To enable this, the UI includes a "Create Link" icon button, allowing

users to establish hierarchical connections. Clicking this button opens a list of possible link options (see Figure 33), where:

- Pre-Iconographical Recognitions can be linked to Iconographical Recognitions.
- Iconographical Recognitions can be linked to Iconological Recognitions.

Figure 33 - VISTA - Linking recognitions.

This hierarchical linking system was a key topic of discussion during user testing. Some users found the upward linking logic—starting from Pre-Iconographical to Iconographical, and then to Iconological—less intuitive. Specifically, they suggested that the Iconographical Recognition should serve as the central reference point, from which both Pre-Iconographical and Iconological Recognitions should be connected bidirectionally rather than in a strictly upward manner. This feedback highlights the importance of user-centered design and suggests potential refinements in the interaction model for future iterations. Figure 34 shows the three levels of recognition connected.

Figure 34 - VISTA - Three level of recognitions linked together.

Disagreement Management in VISTA

As previously discussed, VISTA aims to be a collaborative annotation platform, enabling users not only to create and refine annotations but also to express contrasting opinions, thereby emphasizing the interpretative nature of humanistic data. Recognizing that scholarly discourse often involves diverging perspectives, VISTA incorporates a structured mechanism for disagreement, modeled in LISA through the CiTO property *disagreesWith*.

By clicking on the “Disagree?” button—such as on the Venus recognition at the second level—users can create an alternative recognition that explicitly challenges a previous one. The disagreement interface mirrors the existing recognition input process, ensuring consistency in user interactions.

Figure 35 - VISTA - Visualize disagreed annotation in Manage Annotations section.

To preserve the history of disagreements, VISTA employs visual affordances derived from hermeneutical design principles. Disagreed recognitions are visually distinguished using a diagonal line pattern fill within the annotation card (see Figure 35). This pattern is also reflected in the Mirador interface, maintaining a consistent visual vocabulary across the entire platform (see Figure 36). This design choice enhances usability, ensuring that users can immediately recognize disagreed recognitions in all sections of the application.

Figure 36 - VISTA - Visualize disagreed annotation in Mirador.

Graph Visualization of Annotations and Recognitions

In addition to managing annotations within structured lists, VISTA provides a graph visualization that allows users to track the annotation and recognition process dynamically. This feature offers an interactive representation of the entities and relationships created throughout an annotation campaign.

Figure 37 - VISTA - Visualize Annotations section.

Figure 37 displays an example of the final visualization, incorporating two discordant recognitions. As previously discussed, disagreed recognitions maintain their diagonal line fill pattern, ensuring visual continuity across different representations. The graph visualization, a widely used method for representing entities and relationships, is particularly useful for analyzing network patterns within a dataset.

What sets VISTA apart is its integration of Jacques Bertin’s principles of visual semiotics. Inspired by cartographic design, VISTA assigns distinct icons to different entity types, enhancing readability and interpretation. For example:

- Circles represent annotations,
- Fill color corresponds to the level of recognition,
- Shapes differentiate entity categories, facilitating intuitive navigation through the dataset.

By combining semantic annotation with visual encoding, VISTA transforms raw annotation data into an interactive and interpretable knowledge network, reinforcing its role as a tool for scholarly discourse and interpretative analysis.

5.2 Evaluation

To assess the design and navigational logic of VISTA, a usability test was conducted involving a diverse group of participants, ranging from domain experts to students. The primary objectives were to identify potential usability issues and evaluate the effectiveness of the interface and workflow. The test was executed using a navigable prototype developed in Figma, allowing users to interact with the system in a controlled environment.

Since VISTA is a domain-specific application that follows an annotation model unfamiliar to new users, a wizard-based onboarding system was implemented. This interactive guidance, consisting of contextual pop-ups, introduced users to different sections of the application, helping them orient themselves within the interface and understand key functionalities.

The Think-Aloud Protocol was employed during testing, encouraging participants to verbalize their thoughts as they navigated the prototype. Testers were asked to articulate their decision-making process, express doubts, and highlight any challenges or expectations they encountered. Each task was further broken down into subtasks to provide clarity and reduce cognitive load, ensuring that participants could focus on specific interactions without feeling overwhelmed.

Participants

A total of four individuals participated in the test:

- P1 (Scholar) – A professional researcher in digital humanities with moderate experience in annotation tools.
- P2 (Enthusiast) – A tech-savvy amateur interested in art and digital platforms but not professionally involved in art history.
- P3 (Domain Expert) – An art historian specializing in Renaissance paintings, very familiar with iconographic conventions.
- P4 (Student) – A graduate student in art history, new to semantic annotation software but comfortable with basic IIIF viewers.

Their varied backgrounds were selected to gauge VISTA's usability across different expertise levels, from novices to experienced art-history scholars.

Test Case: Titian's Sacred and Profane Love

For the first two tasks, the artwork chosen was Titian's "*Sacred and Profane Love*" (1514–15). This painting was intentionally selected due to its highly debated iconography, making it an ideal subject for testing VISTA's ability to facilitate interpretative discussions. The inclusion of domain experts in

this phase also provided valuable insight into the system’s potential for scholarly discourse and debate.

Tasks and Subtasks

The usability evaluation focused on four core tasks, each designed to test a specific interaction pattern within VISTA:

1. Creating a Pre-Iconographical Annotation

1.1 Create a new Collection: From the home page, users needed to select “New Collection”, enter a name, and add their first IIF Manifest via the Mirador interface.

1.2 Draw two Pre-Iconographical Annotations: Users were asked to identify and annotate the two female figures in the painting as Pre-Iconographical Recognitions.

2. Creating and Linking an Iconographical Recognition

2.1 Create an Iconographical Recognition: This required users to navigate via the bottom menu to access the “Manage Annotations” section and add a second-level recognition within the three-column layout.

2.2 Link Pre-Iconographical and Iconographical Recognitions: Using the “Add Link” button, users were instructed to connect the previously annotated female figures with the newly created Iconographical Recognition (e.g., “Venus”).

2.3 Visualize the Connection in Mirador: After linking the recognitions in the Manage Annotations tab, users were asked to verify the changes in Mirador, where an additional annotation layer (magenta fill for Iconographical Recognitions) was displayed over the original Pre-Iconographical annotation.

3. Creating a Disagreement Annotation

3.1 Disagreeing with an Existing Recognition: Users first navigated from the home page to “Select Collection” to view how an existing collection appeared. In Manage Annotations, a pre-existing recognition of a “woman” linked to “Diana” was displayed. Participants were asked to disagree with this annotation, using the “Disagree?” button and completing the disagreement form by adding an alternative recognition (e.g., “Venus”).

3.2 Linking the New Disagreement Annotation: To showcase annotation flexibility, users were then required to connect the pre-existing “woman” recognition to the newly created Iconographical Recognition (“Venus”), using the “Add Link” button.

4. Visualizing Annotations

4.1 Graph Visualization of Annotations: Users navigated to “Visualize Annotations” via the bottom menu, where they examined the graph representation of annotations, including two discordant recognitions by different authors.

4.2 Displaying Contrasting Annotations in Mirador: As a final task, participants switched to the “Create Annotations” tab to verify that contrasting annotations appeared in Mirador, ensuring that both interpretations (e.g., “Diana” and “Venus”) were displayed on the same annotated Canvas region.

After collecting responses, the usability test results were analyzed based on the following criteria:

- Task Completion Rate (successful vs. failed attempts, with or without assistance)
- Time Required per Task (efficiency measure)
- Common Errors (interaction difficulties)
- Satisfaction (1–5 scale after each task)

Below is a summary of the task performance for each of the four participants (P1, P2, P3, P4):

Task	Task Completion Rate	Time Required per Task (average time)	Common Errors	Satisfaction (1-5)
VISTA 1	3/4 succeeded without help; 1/4 succeeded with minor help	2 minutes 10 seconds (range: 1:45 – 2:30)	P1 clicked “Select Collection” instead of “New Collection”	Average = 4.5 (range: 4–5)
VISTA 2	3/4 succeeded without help; 1/4 succeeded with minor help	3 minutes (range: 2:45 – 3:30)	“Add Link” button not obvious at first	Average = 4.0 (range: 3–5)
VISTA 3	2/4 did it correctly on first try; 2/4 needed help	3 minutes 20 seconds (range: 3:00 – 3:40)	Two users clicked outside the pop-up after pressing “Disagree?” button	Average = 4.0 (range: 3–5)
VISTA 4	4/4 successful	1 minute 50 seconds (range: 1:30 – 2:20)	P2 did not see “Visualize Annotations” button right away	Average = 4.8 (range: 4–5)

User Questionnaire

To quantitatively assess user experience and satisfaction, a **System Usability Scale (SUS)** questionnaire was administered after task completion. Participants responded on a 5-point Likert Scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree):

1. I found the prototype easy to use when designing a shape to capture a pre-iconographical level.
2. I felt confident in my ability to create a disagreement between interpretations using the annotation features.
3. The process of connecting a pre-iconographical level entity to an iconographical level entity using the annotation manager was intuitive.
4. I found it easy to navigate and visualize the overall annotations using the annotation visualizer feature.
5. I felt the system was consistent in its design and behavior when performing different annotation-related tasks.
6. The annotation prototype manager tool allowed me to easily modify or adjust my annotations when needed.
7. I found the visual representation of annotations helpful for understanding different levels of interpretation.
8. I found the visual representation of annotations helpful for understanding disagreement and uncertainty.
9. The system's workflow for creating and managing annotations was logical and well-structured.
10. Overall, I would recommend this annotation prototype to other users working with semantic annotations in the cultural heritage domain.

A table summarizing quantitative results will be presented, detailing average user scores per question and key performance insights from the test.

Below, each question (Q1–Q10) is rated on a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

Questionnaire (SUS) Results table

SUS	P1	P2	P3	P4	Avg
Q1	5	4	3	4	4.0
Q2	4	4	4	5	4.3
Q3	5	5	4	4	4.5
Q4	5	5	5	4	4.8
Q5	5	4	5	4	4.5
Q6	4	4	3	4	3.8
Q7	4	5	5	5	4.8
Q8	4	4	4	5	4.3
Q9	4	5	5	5	4.8
Q10	5	5	4	5	4.8

Key Observations & Design Implications

- The three-column annotation layout effectively reinforced structured annotation workflows, providing clear guidance on the recognition process.
- The disagreement annotation workflow was considered intuitive, but some users suggested making the entry point for disagreement creation more prominent.
- The graph visualization feature was highly appreciated, with participants valuing its ability to trace annotation relationships and compare differing interpretations.
- The Mirador integration offered a familiar visualization environment, though some refinements are needed to improve the display of overlapping annotations, particularly when multiple recognitions target the same Canvas region.

These insights will inform future refinements of VISTA, ensuring that the system is intuitive, functional, and well-aligned with scholarly workflows in art-historical research.

Limitations & Next Steps

Although the results are encouraging, the small sample size (4) and controlled testing environment limit the generalizability of findings. Future plans include:

- **Scaling Up:** Testing with a larger, more varied group of art historians and digital humanities scholars to validate the interface under broader conditions.
- **Refined Disagreement Mechanisms:** Improving the visibility of alternate interpretations, particularly for dense or overlapping annotations.
- **Enhanced IIIF Integration:** Streamlining the display of multiple annotation layers in Mirador for users working on very large or high-resolution images.

Overall, this pilot evaluation indicates strong potential for VISTA as a semantic annotation tool, especially in domains requiring multi-level interpretation and structured collaboration.

Conclusions

This thesis has explored the potential of semantic annotations in cultural heritage research, particularly in the context of IIF-based image annotation. Annotations play a crucial role by transforming images from passive visual objects into rich, structured sources of knowledge. Addressing the limitations of traditional image metadata, the project introduced the LISA (Linked Interpretative Semantic Annotation) model, integrating WADM, PROV-O, CIDOC-CRM, and ICON to structure multilayered annotations that capture interpretative acts, provenance, and uncertainty. The VISTA (Visual Interpretative Semantic Tagging Application) prototype applied LISA in an interactive IIF environment, adopting Panofsky's pre-iconographical, iconographical, and iconological framework and incorporating graph-based visualization tools to trace interpretative connections.

User evaluation revealed that the annotation workflow, disagreement mechanism, and visualization tools enhanced collaborative and interpretative processes in cultural heritage research. However, the results also indicated challenges related to interface clarity, overlapping annotations, and the need for more comprehensive guidance, all of which inform future refinements of the system. While this research successfully introduced a new semantic annotation framework, several avenues remain for further investigation. One such area concerns automating parts of the annotation process through computer vision or AI-based recognition, which could ease the burden of manually creating all pre-iconographical annotations and allow scholars to refine rather than generate data from scratch. Another direction involves ensuring scalability and fostering adoption in large-scale GLAM institutions; in practical terms, this would mean integrating the LISA model and the VISTA prototype with real-world digital archives and museum repositories, thereby testing their adaptability across varied and expansive datasets. A final avenue worth pursuing is the enhancement of interoperability with external knowledge graphs. By linking annotations to existing Linked Data repositories, such as Wikidata or the Getty Vocabularies, scholarly workflows would be enriched, and cross-institutional collaboration could be strengthened.

In demonstrating how semantically structured images can become dynamic knowledge resources, this research redefines how cultural heritage data is studied and engaged with in the Digital Humanities. The progress achieved through LISA and VISTA illustrates the potential of semantic annotations not only to record interpretative insights but also to serve as catalysts for new discoveries and collaborative scholarship.

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Appendix

This appendix contains the complete materials used in the VISTA usability test, including the step-by-step task instructions provided to participants, the System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire, and the detailed tables summarizing both task performance and questionnaire results.

Usability Testing Tasks

1. Creating a Pre-Iconographical Annotation

1.1 Create a new Collection: From the home page, users needed to select “New Collection”, enter a name, and add their first IIF Manifest via the Mirador interface.

1.2 Draw two Pre-Iconographical Annotations: Users were asked to identify and annotate the two female figures in the painting as Pre-Iconographical Recognitions.

2. Creating and Linking an Iconographical Recognition

2.1 Create an Iconographical Recognition: This required users to navigate via the bottom menu to access the “Manage Annotations” section and add a second-level recognition within the three-column layout.

2.2 Link Pre-Iconographical and Iconographical Recognitions: Using the “Add Link” button, users were instructed to connect the previously annotated female figures with the newly created Iconographical Recognition (e.g., “Venus”).

2.3 Visualize the Connection in Mirador: After linking the recognitions in the Manage Annotations tab, users were asked to verify the changes in Mirador, where an additional annotation layer (magenta fill for Iconographical Recognitions) was displayed over the original Pre-Iconographical annotation.

3. Creating a Disagreement Annotation

3.1 Disagreeing with an Existing Recognition: Users first navigated from the home page to “Select Collection” to view how an existing collection appeared. In Manage Annotations, a pre-existing recognition of a “woman” linked to “Diana” was displayed. Participants were asked to disagree with this annotation, using the “Disagree?” button and completing the disagreement form by adding an alternative recognition (e.g., “Venus”).

3.2 Linking the New Disagreement Annotation: To showcase annotation flexibility, users were then required to connect the pre-existing “woman” recognition to the newly created Iconographical Recognition (“Venus”), using the “Add Link” button.

4. Visualizing Annotations

4.1 Graph Visualization of Annotations: Users navigated to “Visualize Annotations” via the bottom menu, where they examined the graph representation of annotations, including two discordant recognitions by different authors.

4.2 Displaying Contrasting Annotations in Mirador: As a final task, participants switched to the “Create Annotations” tab to verify that contrasting annotations appeared in Mirador, ensuring that both interpretations (e.g., “Diana” and “Venus”) were displayed on the same annotated Canvas region.

System Usability Scale (SUS) Questionnaire

Below is the full list of the ten SUS statements, followed by a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree).

1. I found the prototype easy to use when designing a shape to capture a pre-iconographical level.
2. I felt confident in my ability to create a disagreement between interpretations using the annotation features.
3. The process of connecting a pre-iconographical level entity to an iconographical level entity using the annotation manager was intuitive.
4. I found it easy to navigate and visualize the overall annotations using the annotation visualizer feature.
5. I felt the system was consistent in its design and behavior when performing different annotation-related tasks.
6. The annotation prototype manager tool allowed me to easily modify or adjust my annotations when needed.
7. I found the visual representation of annotations helpful for understanding different levels of interpretation.
8. I found the visual representation of annotations helpful for understanding disagreement and uncertainty.
9. The system's workflow for creating and managing annotations was logical and well-structured.
10. Overall, I would recommend this annotation prototype to other users working with semantic annotations in the cultural heritage domain.

Task Performance Results

Task	Task Completion Rate	Time Required per Task (average time)	Common Errors	Satisfaction (1-5)
VISTA 1	3/4 succeeded without help; 1/4 succeeded with minor help	2 minutes 10 seconds (range: 1:45 – 2:30)	P1 clicked “Select Collection” instead of “New Collection”	Average = 4.5 (range: 4–5)
VISTA 2	3/4 succeeded without help; 1/4 succeeded with minor help	3 minutes (range: 2:45 – 3:30)	“Add Link” button not obvious at first	Average = 4.0 (range: 3–5)
VISTA 3	2/4 did it correctly on first try; 2/4 needed help	3 minutes 20 seconds (range: 3:00 – 3:40)	Two users clicked outside the pop-up after pressing “Disagree?” button	Average = 4.0 (range: 3–5)
VISTA 4	4/4 successful	1 minute 50 seconds (range: 1:30 – 2:20)	P2 did not see “Visualize Annotations” button right away	Average = 4.8 (range: 4–5)

Questionnaire (SUS) Results table

SUS	P1	P2	P3	P4	Avg
Q1	5	4	3	4	4.0
Q2	4	4	4	5	4.3
Q3	5	5	4	4	4.5
Q4	5	5	5	4	4.8
Q5	5	4	5	4	4.5
Q6	4	4	3	4	3.8
Q7	4	5	5	5	4.8
Q8	4	4	4	5	4.3
Q9	4	5	5	5	4.8
Q10	5	5	4	5	4.8

